

Date: Legitimate Crisis Governance

WP7 activities: technical report

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1. Introduction

Work Package 7 (WP7) of the LEGITIMULT project represents the bridge between the academic work produced throughout the project and its translation into real-world impact. WP7 was designed to move beyond traditional dissemination, engaging directly with key societal and institutional actors – policymakers, citizens, journalists, and practitioners – across Europe. Through structured and replicable activities, it aimed to transform theoretical insights into actionable tools and collaborative learning experiences.

The central goal of WP7 was to test and refine the project’s findings in real-life settings. This goal was guided by the recognition that the legitimacy of crisis management depends not only on sound institutional frameworks but also on meaningful engagement, communication, and feedback among stakeholders. The activities of WP7 sought to contribute to narrowing the gap between science, policy, media, and society, one of the key challenges made visible during the Covid-19 pandemic.

To this end, WP7 developed and implemented four complementary formats:

1. **An e-learning course**, available in six languages, designed to support authorities from different levels of governance and civil society actors in understanding and applying key principles of legitimate crisis governance;
2. **Citizens’ juries**, held in four pilot regions, engaging randomly selected citizens in deliberative processes that led to concrete recommendations on present and future crisis management;
3. **Workshops with media and communication experts**, focusing on the role of journalism and public communication in strengthening or weakening crisis legitimacy;
4. **A practitioners’ seminar**, originally conceived as a two-week in-person course, but later adapted into a hybrid format consisting of thematic webinars and meetings, to enable feedback, exchange, and reflection among policy practitioners and researchers.

All four activities were implemented across different pilot areas representing the main European regions (North – Norway and Sweden, South – Italy, East – Slovenia, and Central – Belgium), ensuring a geographically and institutionally diverse testing ground for the tools and methods developed within LEGITIMULT.

Throughout these activities, stakeholders were involved not merely as recipients of knowledge but as co-creators of output. Their participation shaped the structure and content of the final policy recommendations, which were refined based on their real-world insights and feedback. In this way, WP7 embodied the principles of Open Science and citizen engagement promoted by the European Commission, ensuring that research is grounded in the lived realities of the communities it seeks to support.

The results of each activity – e-learning course feedback, citizen recommendations, media feedback, practitioners' engagement —are captured in this report. As to the structure, it will begin with discussing

the development and implementation of the e-learning course, followed by detailed accounts of the citizens' juries and their comparative analysis alongside position papers, then the media workshops and their feedback, and concluding with insights from the practitioners' engagement. The annex comprises all documents developed in WP7.

WP7 demonstrates that translating academic research into practical guidance is not only possible but essential to build more legitimate, inclusive, and effective crisis governance frameworks.

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2. E-learning course

2.1. *Why the E-learning Course?*

The Covid-19 pandemic revealed the pressing need for better preparedness and stronger decision-making capacity at all levels of government, particularly among subnational authorities and civil servants. Many actors were unprepared to address the challenges of a fast-moving crisis while safeguarding fundamental rights, democratic legitimacy, and public trust. This exposed not only structural gaps in governance but also a significant training and knowledge gap among those tasked with crisis response.

To address this, one of the activities of WP7 was to develop a multilingual e-learning course on legitimate crisis governance, aimed at executive leaders, policymakers, civil servants, and civil society in general. The course is designed to equip these key actors with practical knowledge and conceptual tools to better manage crises while respecting democratic norms, human rights, and institutional legitimacy.

Drawing from the research findings of Work Packages 2 to 6, the course transforms complex academic outputs into accessible, thematic learning modules. Topics include the rule of law in emergencies, protection of minority rights, prevention of discrimination, the role of public trust and communication, and the economic implications of crisis governance. Each module is grounded in real-world examples and presents trade-offs and dilemmas faced by decision-makers in high-pressure contexts.

The course is offered in six languages –English, German, French, Spanish, Italian, and Croatian– through Eurac Research’s dedicated learning platform: <https://e-learning.eurac.edu/en/legitimult/#/>. The course is also available on LEGITIMULT official website. By hosting the course on a flexible and accessible platform, the project ensures broad availability and long-term sustainability beyond the project’s lifespan.

The format includes pre-recorded video lectures, real-life examples and interactive quizzes. It is designed for asynchronous participation, allowing learners to follow the course at their own pace. Most importantly, the course is not only a tool for individual learning, but also a way to foster collective reflection across institutions and countries.

Beyond its educational value, the e-learning course plays a strategic role within WP7: it links research and policy, empowers public officials, and serves as a gateway for further engagement in the project’s participatory activities – such as citizen juries and practitioner dialogues. It is also a replicable and adaptable model for future training efforts in the field of democratic crisis governance.

In short, the e-learning course is a cornerstone of LEGITIMULT’s commitment to turning research into practice, by delivering knowledge in a way that is inclusive, practical, and ready to meet the real demands of future crises.

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2.2. How did we do it concretely? The development of the e-learning course

The e-learning course under WP7 was built through a structured, collaborative process that combined academic insight, practical relevance, design sensibility, and multilingual accessibility. It was designed to deliver timely training on legitimate crisis governance to policymakers, civil servants, and organized civil society across Europe.

Step 1 – Content design and module identification

Based on Work Packages 1 through 6, we identified six topics for the course lessons, each focusing on a specific aspect of legitimacy during crises. EURAC Research worked with WP leads to translate these research findings into clear learning objectives and lesson outlines.

Step 2 – Multimedia content creation

Experts—including scholars and practitioners – recorded through video interviews concise video lessons (each 10-20 minutes), focusing on key dilemmas, frameworks, and real-life governance trade-offs in a simple and understandable way. Each lesson was complemented by text, real-life examples, key recommendations for policymakers and practitioners, and interactive quizzes. A visually pleasant design ensured consistency and aesthetic appeal across lessons and materials.

Step 3 – Multilingual production

While the master content was created in English, the entire course was subtitled and translated into German, French, Italian, Spanish, and Croatian. Translation duties were handled by native speakers at the partner institutions to guarantee linguistic accuracy and contextual relevance. All supporting documents (quizzes, recommendations, texts) were likewise translated.

Step 4 – Platform integration

The course was launched on Eurac’s e-learning portal (elearning.eurac.edu/en/legitimult/), chosen for its flexible, user-friendly interface. Learners could access all modules independently, complete quizzes, at any time, in any language. The platform design supports self-paced learning and streamlined navigation.

Step 5 – Broad promotion and feedback gathering

The course was broadly promoted via networks of project partners, stakeholders, and institutional contacts across Europe. We asked also for feedback (module completion rates, quiz scores, usage analytics).

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Step 6 – Iterative refinement

Collected feedback from all the partners was received by the WP7 coordination team to revise both form and content at multiple stages throughout the course production. Once the course was finalized, some last additional adjustments were made on the basis of comments. This process balanced academic rigor with usability and practicality. By the course's launch, the outcome was a multilingual, research-rooted, and professionally designed learning tool—built to equip current and future practitioners with valuable knowledge on legitimate crisis governance.

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3. Citizens' Juries (CJs)

3.1. Why CJs?

Citizens' Juries (CJs) represent a democratic innovation within the broader framework of deliberative and participatory democracy. As a method rooted in democratic renewal, CJs bring together a small, diverse group of randomly selected citizens to deliberate on complex policy questions, offering considered recommendations grounded in shared reasoning. This model enables everyday people – non-experts – to engage directly in the policymaking process, bridging the gap between institutions and society.

Typically composed of 12 to 24 participants, CJs are structured to foster inclusive, respectful, and evidence-based dialogue. Participants are selected through a process of sortition, often from electoral rolls or population registries, ensuring demographic diversity in terms of age, gender, education level, and geographic location. This diversity is a key strength of the model: it reflects the broader public and helps mitigate the influence of organized interests or elite actors.

Before deliberation begins, jurors are provided with balanced, accessible, and comprehensive information on the topic at hand – through expert presentations, written materials, and facilitated Q&A sessions. This knowledge equips participants to engage critically with the issues and one another, forming arguments and judgments based on evidence rather than opinion alone.

At the heart of a CJ is deliberation. Guided by trained facilitators, participants share perspectives, test ideas, ask questions, and refine their views through collective reasoning. After extended discussion, the group collaboratively drafts a set of recommendations or a position paper, which is then shared with relevant decision-makers, institutions, or the public.

The value of CJs lies not only in the recommendations they produce but also in their democratic ethos: they give ordinary citizens a meaningful voice in shaping decisions that affect their communities. In doing so, they help counteract political disengagement and rebuild trust in governance by demonstrating that people can contribute constructively to complex policy debates.

Citizens' Juries have been implemented in a range of countries and policy areas – from healthcare to urban planning to climate change – proving their versatility and legitimacy. In the context of LEGITIMULT, CJs were used to explore legitimacy in crisis governance, creating space for citizens to reflect on the challenges, trade-offs, and democratic values at stake in emergency decision-making. By combining rigorous methodology with public participation, CJs stand as a powerful tool for more responsive and inclusive crisis governance.

3.2. How did we do it concretely? The development of the CJs

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The Citizens' Juries (CJs) were conceived as a participatory mechanism to directly involve ordinary citizens in the reflection on, and co-creation of, recommendations for more legitimate crisis governance. They were built on the premise that democratic legitimacy depends not only on institutional arrangements, but also on the active inclusion of citizens' voices – particularly in times of crisis, when decisions are taken swiftly and often with limited public consultation.

Four pilot areas were selected for the implementation of the CJs: Italy (Bolzano/ Bozen), Slovenia (Izola), Belgium (Huldenberg), and Norway (Bergen). These regions were chosen to reflect the diversity of European governance systems and crisis responses. Each pilot represented a distinct region of Europe (South, East, Central, and North), allowing for contextual variation. Two of the pilot areas – Izola and Huldenberg – are relatively small municipalities, while Bolzano and Bergen represent medium-sized cities. This variation in size allowed for testing the Citizen Jury model in different administrative and demographic contexts.

To ensure methodological coherence, Eurac Research designed a shared framework for all juries, detailing the structure, facilitation approach, ethical standards, and output format. However, the actual design was then **contextualized and elaborated together with local partners and the involved municipalities that were contacted directly by the partners**. This ensured comparability across sites while allowing local partners to adapt delivery to their specific contexts. Each jury was intended to bring together around 15 citizens for a one-day deliberative event, conducted in the local language and focused on one major theme derived from LEGITIMULT's research.

The development of each CJ followed a common set of steps:

1. Designing the Jury Process

Eurac, together with local partners, developed a structure that included opening presentations on the project, expert inputs on project results, deliberative phase with breakout discussions, and a plenary session to co-create recommendations and a final position paper. Local project teams were responsible for selecting the CJ topic based on the work packages most relevant to their expertise.

2. Preparing Materials

Eurac prepared a set of supporting materials to facilitate the process, such as a draft invitation letter, an evaluation form for citizens, a template for position papers, and the required ethical forms that were then shared with all the partners.

3. Recruiting Participants

Citizens in two pilot sites were recruited through a random selection process (sortition), supported by outreach strategies including institutional letters. In two cases the random selection was replaced by alternative recruitment, like open calls on both paper and online formats. Those citizens who agreed to participate received a small incentive and/or a participation kit. Ultimately, 5–18 participants were

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engaged in each jury, reflecting a mix of ages, genders, educational backgrounds, and professional experiences.

4. Supporting Facilitators

Facilitators were briefed by Eurac, outlining the goals, structure, and ethical rules of the CJ process. Where needed, teams were supported by backup staff to ensure smooth organisation and technical reliability.

5. Implementation

Each CJ was held in person, with lead and support by the responsible local partner ensuring logistical aspects were well managed. Events took place in accessible venues, and local teams ensured materials were available in the appropriate language. The WP Leader (Eurac research) supported all juries remotely to guarantee consistency.

6. Documentation and Output

Each CJ concluded in the production of a position paper by the local partner summarizing the procedure, the deliberations and outlining concrete citizen recommendations. A shared reporting template allowed local partners to compile and communicate results consistently. These outputs were translated into English and disseminated to the broader consortium and relevant stakeholders.

7. Flexibility and Adaptation

Despite careful planning, local realities required adaptability. In some cases, participation was lower than anticipated or scheduling conflicts emerged. Local teams adjusted the format where necessary for example, increasing support staff, or modifying the planned structure of the event – to maintain inclusiveness and quality.

The CJs were not only useful in generating bottom-up policy proposals but also served as powerful exercises in democratic engagement. Participants in all pilot regions filled in an evaluation form after the event and described the process as empowering, informative, and impactful. Their reflections contributed directly to LEGITIMULT's final policy recommendations, bringing grounded, real-life perspectives into the broader academic and institutional discussion.

3.3. Comparative analysis of CJs and the position papers

Legitimult's CJs were held in March 2025 in the cities of Bolzano/Bozen, Izola/Isola and Huldenberg and in August 2025 in Bergen. The size of the juries consisted of 5 to 18 persons (Huldenberg: 5; Bolzano: 8; Izola: 11; Bergen: 18). It should be noted that in each pilot site the composition differed in the fields of activity of the participants.

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Also, the selection process of the participants was different. In Bolzano/Bozen and Bergen, participants were selected using a random selection, in Bolzano/Bozen supported by an open call. In Izola/Isola, information about the event was posted on the Municipality's website, and the invitation was published by local and regional mass media, in particular, on local radio. In Huldenberg, the announcement was published in the municipal newspaper, on social networks of the official account of the municipality.

During the preparation of the citizen juries, various obstacles to citizen participation were identified. In Huldenberg, the main challenge was the lack of response from the population, in Izola/Isola, national legislation prohibiting the use of voter lists for the random selection has become a key barrier. In Bolzano/Bozen, the main challenges were the coincidence of city events on the day of the citizen jury, organizational difficulties in planning the lottery, as well as bureaucratic delays that affected the timeliness of sending invitations – as a result, only 8 participants were gathered instead of the planned 15.

All four events were held in the format of one day event and lasted 5-6 hours. They followed a common structure but were adapted to local needs. In three cases the event took place in two languages (German/Italian in Bolzano/Bozen; English/Norwegian in Bergen; Italian/Slovenian in Izola/Isola). The juries especially differed in the topics of discussion and/or guiding questions during the deliberative phase, however, they all touched on potential scenarios for future crisis. In Bolzano/Bozen and Bergen the events were divided into several clearly defined phases, and the participants were divided into subgroups for a more detailed discussion before they were reunited in a plenary phase.

In Bolzano the discussion focused on a potential crisis of climate change and temperature increase. In Bergen, participants were first presented with a hypothetical scenario that the municipality is drafting an emergency preparedness plan and is seeking recommendations based on citizens' experiences during the Covid-19 crisis. They were then divided into four sub-groups, each tasked with selecting two or three guiding questions. The most chosen question was: Drawing on your experience of the Covid-19 crisis, which measures worked well, and which ones did not work well? In Izola/Isola, the event also consisted of two parts, the format was based on an open discussion using guiding questions on legality, proportionality and legitimacy of measures in crisis situations. The discussion was conducted by all participants together. In Huldenberg, given the small number of participants, the discussion was organized in the form of plenary discussions. It included two stages: first, a discussion of general crisis scenarios based on the research of the project, then hypothetical situations related to the municipality. After the deliberation phase, the participants in all assemblies formulated recommendations and summed up the results.

The elaborated recommendations varied due to the diversity of focus topics and specific guiding questions asked by the experts and facilitators. The recommendations reflect on the one hand distinct local priorities, shaped by the contexts and concerns of each community but on the other hand also similar approaches to crisis management: Bolzano/Bozen's position paper emphasized environmental challenges, proposing targeted measures to combat potential heatwaves and water shortages, with clear, actionable recommendations directed at municipal and provincial authorities. In contrast, Izola/Isola's

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paper focused on improving the legitimacy, effectiveness, and transparency of crisis management, advocating for stronger professional involvement, clearer authority divisions, and enhanced public communication and anti-corruption efforts. Huldenberg's recommendations highlighted the layered nature of governance during crises, stressing trust in federal and European-level mandates while promoting increased local engagement and transparent communication. Additionally, Huldenberg's collaboration with municipal authorities resulted in practical recommendations on emergency planning, information dissemination, and data security tailored to local needs. In Bergen, the recommendations focus on improving crisis communication, including diverse and accessible information channels and ensuring experts deliver credible messaging. They emphasize the need for better preparedness and planning, such as independent emergency councils or professional panels.

Collectively, the final recommendations of the citizens illustrate how each municipality's experiences and challenges shape their priorities, ranging from environmental resilience to governance clarity and crisis communication, underscoring the need for context-sensitive policies in crisis preparedness and response. A common result of all juries is the importance of better transparent crisis communication by the institutions and the wish for inclusive governance. These two aspects were included in all discussions and recommendations, independently where the citizen assembly took place. This supports the research of the project that transparent information and continuous communication during a crisis is key. In Bolzano, Bergen and Huldenberg the participants even talked about the importance of emergency plans.

Here some details on the single recommendations by the citizens:

In Bolzano/Bozen 10 concrete recommendations were addressed to the Municipality, the Province, and other relevant bodies. Ultimately, two recommendations received the most votes:

1. Introduce specific measures to combat heat in the municipal urban planning strategy (e.g., increasing green spaces, installing accessible drinking water points for all)
2. Create water reserves (directed to the Provincial authorities).

In Izola/Isola, recommendations were drafted on two general guiding questions: "*How crisis management and measures can be improved (according to COVID-19 pandemic experience), and how to ensure their proportionality, effectiveness, and legitimacy in future crisis situations.*" All the recommendations could be formed into four main categories:

1. Greater involvement and visibility of professionals in crisis management;
2. A clearer division of roles between central and local authorities;
3. More fact-based communication of measures, along with broader public consultation;
4. The need for stronger measures to tackle corruption in public procurement during crises.

In Huldenberg, recommendations were developed in two phases. The first phase focused on the guiding question: "*Which level of government is most trusted during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic?*" In the second phase, participants discussed crisis-related scenarios specific to Huldenberg, with a particular

emphasis on citizens' preferences regarding communication from the municipality and its actions in informing and engaging with residents during emergency situations.

First phase recommendations:

1. The main rules, in times of crisis, should be mandated from the country or even the European level;
2. The subnational levels, and especially the local level, should be increasingly involved in crisis management and implementation of measures during the crisis, while in the first phases of crisis the federal levels can unilaterally decide;
3. The reason behind measures and the (scientific) grounds for them should be explicated.

Second phase recommendations (were elaborated in collaboration with municipality):

1. An emergency plan had to be in place, which should be well thought out ahead of time and with the necessary expertise
2. Citizens recommended ensuring transparency and accessibility of crisis information through a variety of channels, including the municipality's official website, local media and information boards, as well as using the BE-alert system or a separate Huldenberg notification
3. The identity card should always remain available to get replaced or requested
4. In case of data breaches or hacks, the municipality should inform the citizens of what information about them is possibly shared, which risks are involved in this, and whether there is action required from the citizen.

Lastly, in Bergen a total of eleven recommendations were developed:

1. More accessible information channels, social media, text messages, local radio. A website that is updated continuously, functions as a secure source that makes it easy for individuals to access the latest information.
2. The government must create a good emergency plan if the other information channels are down. Information should be available at grocery stores. Air raid sirens.
3. The public sector must prioritize service telephones and create a contingency plan in the event of an emergency and people call much more than usual.
4. Crisis management should not be politically driven. The recommendation is to protect children and young people from isolating measures and conduct frequent assessments of the measures, and that it is communicated to the people via the right people (professionals must be up and coming). The purpose of frequent assessments is to ensure legitimacy throughout the crisis period.
5. Form an independent emergency council, with professional groups, interest organizations, voluntary emergency organizations (lawyers, health care, schools, industry, etc.) The purpose is to improve professional competence, communication, appropriate measures. Create a holistic picture of the situation.
6. Those who are going to communicate crisis decisions to the people must be experts and professionals in the field, who are also credible. Be honest with all information that is given.

7. Resources we need are money and professionals. We think that other actors are important are the government and professionals. We believe that professionals should form a professional panel that is formed by professionals with expertise in the different crises that occur and based on risk analysis. That is, to carry out a certain prevention.
8. Citizens' panel responds to things in BK (Bergen municipality transcript note?). Use them as help, if it is built up in such a way that it is a diversified group. Listen to them, feel that you are heard. Disabled and pensioners as voluntary labor. Or people who have a lot of surplus. Motivate to participate in voluntary work and still do their job.
9. Minimum possible shutdown (a middle ground). Every other day at school, prioritize children and young people. Quick solutions such as teams in school. The cabin ban should have been handled differently. Sent home from FHS and the military. All occupational groups must be allowed to have protective equipment.
10. Primarily use all relevant digital and analogue means for raising initial awareness. This should as a minimum include the main issue and where further information is available. Initial measures (national) with expected reassessment dates, follow up local measures, make information available for minority languages.
11. Initially, any measure should be applicable on a national level. This should have a short timeframe before measures are reassessed. Once the situation is more transparent, measures can be changed.

On the organizational side, according to the feedback, the events in all pilot regions were very successful. In all pilot areas the evaluation forms show that the events were positively assessed by participants, and they also appreciated the topic evaluating it as highly relevant. Partner reported that citizens in all events were highly engaged in the discussions.

Nonetheless the overall positive feedback, the partner institutions also faced some challenges before or during the implementation.

In Bolzano/Bozen, the organization of the Citizens' Jury faced several challenges: Participation was lower than originally planned, partly due to bureaucratic and logistical difficulties in coordinating with the municipal administration. During the event, time constraints limited the depth of the discussion phase, and clearer instructions would have been useful for the follow-up activities. The local team also noted the need for a backup facilitator to ensure smooth moderation.

In Izola/Isola, one of the challenges in organizing the event was also the difficulty of attracting citizens to participate in the jury. During the event, the appearance of conspiracy theories during the discussions was noted as another challenge, but this did not dominate the discussion and did not affect the main dialogue. After the citizen jury, it was concluded that in the future it is necessary to involve certain groups of the population and their representatives in crisis management processes in order to ensure greater legitimacy of measures taken by government agencies.

4. Media Workshops (MWs)

4.1 Why MWs?

In times of crisis, communication is not merely a support function, it becomes a central pillar of governance. The way information is conveyed, filtered, or withheld can shape public trust, influence behavior, and determine the perceived legitimacy of political decisions. In this context, the media plays a crucial role at the intersection of science, policy, and the public. It is both a messenger and a stakeholder, capable of amplifying transparency or, conversely, revealing the cracks in institutional responses.

The LEGITIMULT Media Workshops (MWs) were designed to engage these crucial actors. These events brought together journalists, media professionals, and institutional communication experts to reflect on the role of media in crisis situations. Grounded in the project's findings the workshops created a space to discuss key challenges such as the restriction of media freedoms, institutional barriers to information during emergencies, and the growing risks of misinformation and public distrust.

The participants were invited to examine not only how media actors operate under pressure, but also how their engagement – or exclusion – can influence the broader legitimacy of crisis governance. The objective was twofold: to ensure that media professionals were informed of the project's key findings, and to collaboratively explore how these findings could be translated into more transparent, accountable, and participatory communication practices during crises. Media actors were not seen merely as recipients of research but as co-creators of knowledge and solutions.

Each interactive workshop aimed to produce concrete outcomes: a set of recommendations on how media institutions, government communication offices, and journalists themselves can strengthen their contribution to legitimate crisis management. These insights were then fed back into the project's final toolbox and policy outputs.

In short, the Media Workshops served a dual function, disseminating research findings and activating professional dialogue among a key community of practice. They recognized that no crisis can be managed legitimately without open, reliable, and responsible communication – and that such communication depends on empowering those who shape the public narrative.

4.2 How we did it concretely? The development of the MWs

The Media Workshops were conceived as one-day participatory events aimed at involving journalists, media professionals, and institutional communication experts in reflecting on the role of media during crises. These workshops played a critical role in bridging research findings with the real-world practices of media communication, especially in times when trust, transparency, and legitimacy are at stake.

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The development of the workshops began with the drafting of a shared concept note, coordinated by Eurac Research, which laid out a flexible yet coherent structure to be adapted across the four pilot areas – Belgium (UAnt), Italy (Eurac), Sweden (IntIdea), and Slovenia (IES). Each local partner was responsible for implementing the workshop within their national or regional context, taking into account linguistic, cultural, and institutional specificities.

To ensure comparability across countries, a common methodological framework was provided. This included:

- a suggested agenda broken into introductory remarks, keynote speech, project findings presentation, and interactive discussion;
- guiding questions, such as: What role should the media play in a crisis so that it can be considered legitimately managed? How to manage communication in emergency situations? What mistakes should be avoided, looking back at how the pandemic was handled? How could the flow of information between institutions (particularly the provincial level, but also regional authorities, the national government, ministries, parliament, and the WHO) and the media be improved?
- templates for participant lists, invitations, feedback collection, and ethics/privacy compliance.

The structure of each workshop included four key phases:

1. **Introduction to the LEGITIMULT project**, including its research questions and goals;
2. **Keynote input** from a high-profile speaker or academic, chosen for their expertise in media or crisis communication, to draw interest and frame the discussion;
3. **Presentation of project findings**, especially from the Citizens' Juries or relevant WPs, with a focus on issues such as media freedom, access to information, and crisis legitimacy;
4. **Interactive brainstorming or group sessions**, where participants discussed their experiences during past crises, challenges faced in public communication and contributed concrete suggestions on how the media can enhance legitimacy in crisis contexts.

Special attention was paid to participants' selection. Invitations targeted journalists across formats (print, television, radio, digital), institutional spokespersons, and media trainers. In several cases, collaboration with local or national journalist associations was pursued, not only to broaden outreach but also to offer participants professional development credits – a move that helped increase participation and interest.

To support inclusive and productive discussions, local partners prepared concise and accessible background materials and facilitated sessions using experienced moderators. In some cases, findings from the Citizens' Juries were presented by participants themselves, linking public expectations with media responsibilities.

The workshops ended with the production of summary reports. Each partner used a standardized reporting template to capture the structure of the event, participant feedback, key ideas that emerged,

and any practical recommendations. These outputs were then shared within the consortium and contributed to the overall analysis presented in the final report and toolbox.

Across the four pilot areas, the MWs demonstrated how targeted engagement with media professionals can amplify the reach and relevance of research, promote democratic dialogue, and foster shared understanding of legitimate crisis governance (see next section).

4.3 Comparative analysis of the MWs and feedback

As a part of LEGITIMULT project, four Media Workshops were held in April and May 2025 in Bolzano, Stockholm, Ljubljana and Antwerp. Each Workshop had its own topic of discussion.

In each pilot area there was different number and composition of participants (10 to 21). In Bolzano there were 10 participants representing local media (print, radio, tv, online) and communication managers (institutional, NGO), in Stockholm total number of participants – 15, there were journalists, alongside journalism students, in Ljubljana 10 participants, representing journalism and academia and in Antwerp - 21 participants, consisting only of students.

The selection process of participants varied in each municipality. For example, in Bolzano participants were invited through targeted individual invitations and internal communication from the Trentino-Alto Adige/South Tyrol Journalists' Association, while in Stockholm participants were selected via email, social media, professional contacts, in Ljubljana – by phone and mail and in Antwerp the media workshop was part of a lecture for journalism students at the *AP Hogeschool* and attendance for students was mandatory.

All four workshops were held in the format of one-day events. In three out of 4 workshops the thematical focus lied in the crisis communication and media during the pandemic, the workshop in Antwerp focused on the question of how scientific results should be communicated. In Bolzano the core of the workshop was the group activity where participants discussed their experience with crisis management and then presented the outcomes, while in Stockholm workshop was built around discussions, where the journalists' insights helped bridge theory with real-world challenges, adding depth to the conversation. In Antwerp as well as in Ljubljana, it was also discussion format, but as in Antwerp there were only students, it included an additional learning component for them.

Before and during the workshops, several challenges were identified. In Bolzano, Antwerp as well as in Stockholm, the main challenge was related to recruiting participants: it was not easy to find journalists willing to attend the workshop. In Ljubljana, no challenges were identified during the Media Workshop. In Bolzano, the main challenge was designing an interesting format to attract participants and have a concrete impact on the work of media professionals. While, in Stockholm, the main challenge was the discrepancy between the expected and actual audience – both in terms of number and composition. This also led to organizational difficulties, including an oversized conference room.

Each Media Workshop elaborated specific recommendations, shaped by the specific topics discussed and the diverse backgrounds of the participants.

- In Bolzano, the discussion focused on the topic: ***“Communicating Crisis: The Role of the Media.”***

During the discussion, participants reached the following conclusions. The media play a crucial role in upholding democracy by providing citizens with reliable information, especially during crises, so they can form their own informed opinions. Participants emphasized the need for a serious and impartial analysis of the mistakes made by journalists during the pandemic, as well as the importance of clearly defining the end of a crisis period to begin a shared process of reflection. At the provincial level, work has already begun on developing guidelines for crisis communication. It was also highlighted that while journalists adhere to ethical standards, other communicators – such as bloggers and opinion leaders on social media – are not bound by the same codes, which can blur the line between facts and opinions, fuel misinformation and sensationalism, and ultimately erode public trust in credible journalism. In this context, participants stressed the need to develop an ethical code for the use of artificial intelligence in media and communication.

- In Stockholm, the topic was ***“Lessons from COVID-19: Journalism in a Post-Pandemic Future.”***

Key discussions during the workshop highlighted the following points. Participants emphasized the critical need for consistent and coherent messaging, particularly in the early stages of a crisis, as fragmented or contradictory narratives can mislead the public. It was noted that journalists often lack the necessary expertise to cover complex crises in depth, underscoring the need to develop specialized journalism. Urgency must not come at the cost of accuracy, nuance and public understanding. Also, during complex crises, journalistic objectivity should not necessarily equate to constant skepticism, but rather to fair engagement with authoritative expertise. Participants stressed the importance of improving digital literacy across all age groups to address the influence of echo chambers and unverified sources on social media. Finally, AI technologies were recognized both as a challenge, due to their potential to amplify misinformation, and as a valuable tool for fact-checking and enhancing media engagement when used responsibly. Also, additional policy recommendations were formulated for Governments and Public Institutions, for Journalists and Media Organizations, and Civil Society and Academia.

- In Ljubljana, the topic for discussion was: ***“Crisis communication and media during the COVID-19 Pandemic and proposals for future crisis situations.”***

Based on the experience of crisis management, information dissemination, and communication during the COVID-19 pandemic, several key lessons for the future were highlighted. There is an urgent need for legislative reform to ensure the stable functioning of media, particularly public information services, and to secure adequate funding for institutions like RTVSLO and STA. Crisis communication must become more proactive, pre-planned, technically equipped, and professionally trained to maintain credibility and public trust. It is also essential to strengthen the crisis infrastructure by diversifying communication channels beyond digital platforms to include analogue systems such as radio frequencies and local community-based networks. Furthermore, greater emphasis should be placed on the role of civil society, with a focus

on building resilient local communities and civic networks capable of responding swiftly and effectively in times of crisis.

- In Antwerp the topic was – ***“How should scientific research be communicated/reported?”***

During the session, participants explored how journalists can engage more effectively with scientific research, highlighting key differences between interviewing scientists and politicians. The training included practice interviews with experts Peter Bursens and Jakob Frateur, followed by feedback sessions focusing on both the structure and substance of the questions posed. Participants also discussed possible options for media coverage of the findings of the LEGITIMULT project. The session briefly touched upon public trust in government during the pandemic and the role of media in covering aspects of crisis governance, emphasizing the importance of maintaining a critical stance without undermining public confidence in governmental measures.

Overall, all four Media Workshops were successful. Participants expressed their gratitude to the organizers for creating an open space for dialogue and initiating a discussion on crisis communication using the COVID-19 pandemic as a case study. For many, this was the first opportunity since the start of the pandemic to reflect on how information is managed during crisis, to reconsider their own roles, acknowledge past mistakes, and think about how to act differently in the future.

In all locations – Bolzano, Stockholm, Ljubljana, and Antwerp – the event was praised for its high level of organization, the depth of the discussions, and the relevance of the topics raised. Participants described the atmosphere as welcoming and inclusive. They commended the moderation and diversity of perspectives presented. Despite some remarks about the duration of the event and limited awareness among key decision makers, most participants stated that they had gained useful insights and recommendations applicable to their future work.

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5. Practitioners Engagement

Originally envisaged as a two-week residential seminar in Fribourg, the practitioners' engagement component of WP7 was reimagined as a more flexible and inclusive format. Considering logistical constraints and the evolving needs of the target audience, the LEGITIMULT consortium opted for a dynamic series of webinars and short in-person seminars. This approach allowed broader participation, thematic flexibility, and deeper contextualization of LEGITIMULT's research findings.

Instead of a single, centralized event, we created a curated series of practitioner-focused sessions, designed to connect crisis governance research with the lived experiences of policymakers, civil servants, and experts operating in multi-level systems. These events were developed to promote two-way learning: disseminating the project's outcomes while collecting practitioners' reactions, needs, and reflections to refine our final outputs.

The series included:

- Webinars featuring cross-national perspectives and dialogue among academics and practitioners. Key topics included:
 - *"Acting Legitimacy in Times of Crisis"* (22 May 2025) – reflections on decision-making under pressure;
 - *"Economic and Social Responses to COVID-19 in Multilevel Systems"* (24 June 2025) – part of the "Turn on Federalism" series;
 - *"Intergovernmental Coordination in Crisis Management: Lessons from Canada and Europe"* (22 July 2025);
 - "From crisis to confidence: how can decision-makers increase trust in times of crisis? (11 September 2025) in collaboration with MEIRSS Middle East Institute for Research and Strategic Studies in Beirut;
 - *"Crisis governance: leaving no one and no place behind"* (18 September 2025) in collaboration with NALAS.
- In-person seminar for more direct engagement, such as:
 - *Presentation of LEGITIMULT findings to the Council of Municipalities of the EGCT European Region Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino* (24 September 2025);

Each of these engagements combined research dissemination with dialogue, using materials from the e-learning course, media workshops, and citizens' juries to contextualize discussions. Participants were invited to provide feedback through open discussion and structured reflection, which directly informed the final toolbox and policy recommendations.

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This decentralized and thematic approach allowed for:

- Greater outreach, engaging participants across geographies, governance levels, and policy domains;
- Contextual adaptation, tailoring content to local or regional institutional realities;
- and timely dissemination, aligning with key moments of project visibility and stakeholder relevance.

Ultimately, the Practitioners' Engagement Path highlighted the importance of co-creation and adaptability in translating research into action. It underscored that legitimacy in crisis governance is not only about academic insight, but about sustained, practical dialogue with those on the frontlines of public decision-making.

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6. Annexes

- a. CJs Information and consent form
- b. CJs Recommendations form
- c. CJs Evaluation Form
- d. CJs Position Papers
 - Bolzano/Bozen
 - Huldernberg
 - Isola/Izola
 - Bergen
- e. MWs Evaluation Form
- f. MWs Output document Form
- g. MWs Output documents
 - Antwerp
 - Ljubljana
 - Stockholm
 - Bolzano/Bozen

a. Information and consent form

Citizens' jury – research project LEGITIMULT

You have been invited to participate in this research activity. Before you agree to participate, please read all the information provided carefully, and do not hesitate to reach out with any questions.

INFORMATION ON THE PROJECT AND ITS AIM

The research activity described below is part of the research project LEGITIMULT. LEGITIMULT is a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Call HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01 (GA Nr. 101061550). This project has also received additional funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

The objective of the LEGITIMULT project is to create and develop the concept of legitimate crisis governance, as it is crucial for maintaining democratic standards in crisis situations and prevents social fragmentation and alienation. It does so by assessing the impact of the measures taken by various international, national and subnational governments in the wake of the Covid-19 pandemic. The project analyzes the effect of these measures, highlighting to what extent multilevel governance influences their impact on democracy, favoring a model of legitimate crisis management. Its final policy recommendations and practical tools will merge into a toolkit for legitimate crisis management, available for use in potential future crises.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION AND RIGHT TO WITHDRAWAL

Participation in this research activity is voluntary. Every citizen may withdraw their consent to participate at any time, without any obligation to provide reasons and without incurring any disadvantage.

AIM OF THIS RESEARCH ACTIVITY AND ITS PROCESS

This Citizens' Assembly is a specific research activity within the LEGITIMULT project and aims to strengthen opportunities for democratic dialogue between citizens and public decision-makers. The involvement of a group of citizens is necessary to integrate their opinions and suggestions into the broader scientific research carried out within the LEGITIMULT project. The specific objective of this activity is to enable citizens to develop proposals and potential measures for managing future crises for the Municipality of XXX and the European Commission.

The concrete process of this activity will follow these steps: a citizens' meeting on XXX (as per the invitation letter received by selected citizens), and deliberation on proposals and potential measures for managing future crises; collection and evaluation of these by the researchers involved in the project; presentation of the outcomes to the new City Council and Municipal Board; inclusion of the proposals in a final report for the LEGITIMULT project to be submitted to the European Commission (by September 2025) along with recommendations emerging from similar assemblies in three other European countries, with the goal of influencing European policies.

RISKS AND BENEFITS OF THIS RESEARCH ACTIVITY

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Participation in this study does not pose any risk to citizens. All personal data collected (such as participants' names and expressed opinions) will be used exclusively for scientific purposes and will be analyzed and stored in an anonymous form.

Benefits to participating in this study include aid to the wider community in the development of legitimate governance in future potential crisis situations, as well as the opportunity to be part of a participatory democracy exercise. No other direct benefits to the participants can be expected.

DISSEMINATION OF PROJECT RESULTS

The proposals and measures deliberated by citizens during the Citizens' Jury will be shared with participants in the form of a position paper prepared by the researchers involved in the project. The content of this position paper will then be incorporated into the results of the LEGITIMULT project (in the form of scientific reports), which will be available from September 2025 upon the project's completion and freely accessible online at <https://legitimult.eu/>.

CONTACT PERSON

For any questions regarding this research activity, please contact one contact person of local team, email.

PARTICIPANT CONSENT

- I have read and understood the information about the study. My questions have been fully and satisfactorily answered.
- I voluntarily consent to participate in this research activity.
- I am aware that I can withdraw my participation at any time by notifying the designated contact person, without any obligation to provide reasons and without incurring any disadvantage.
- I have received a copy of this Information and Consent Form.

NAME SURNAME

PLACE, DATE and SIGNATURE

CONTACT PERSON DECLARATION

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- I have explained the nature and purpose of this research study, the procedures to be undertaken and any risks that may be involved. I have offered to answer any questions and fully answered such questions. I believe that the participant understands my explanation and has freely given informed consent.

NAME SURNAME

PLACE, DATE and SIGNATURE

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b. Citizens' Recommendations Form

Citizens' jury "title"

Place and Date

As a group of citizens gathered today at XXX to discuss the topic "**Managing Present and Future Crises**" within the LEGITIMULT research project, we have developed the following recommendations addressed to the XXX and the European Commission.

We are in XXX in the year 2030, and the city is facing the following crisis scenario:

As citizens, we suggest the following recommendations to manage it in the best possible way:

RECOMMENDATION no.1	
TITLE	
PROPOSAL ADDRESSED TO	
DESCRIPTION	<p><i>What resources?</i></p> <p><i>Which actors?</i></p> <p><i>What action plan?</i></p> <p><i>What timeline?</i></p> <p><i>What other factors should be considered?</i></p> <p><i>[...]</i></p>

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MOTIVATION	

RECOMMENDATION no.2	
TITLE	
PROPOSAL ADDRESSED TO	
DESCRIPTION	
MOTIVATION	

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RECOMMENDATION no.3	
TITLE	
PROPOSAL ADDRESSED TO	
DESCRIPTION	
MOTIVATION	

RECOMMENDATION no.4

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TITLE	
PROPOSAL ADDRESSED TO	
DESCRIPTION	
MOTIVATION	

RECOMMENDATION no.5	
TITLE	
PROPOSAL ADDRESSED TO	

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DESCRIPTION	
MOTIVATION	

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c. CJs Evaluation Form

Media workshop “Title”

Place, Date

How do you evaluate the citizens’ jury overall?

1 very badly	2	3	4	5 very well

Did the citizens’ jury meet your expectations?

- Yes
- No
- Only in part
- No answer

Which aspects did you like the most and which ones the least?

Do you think that the topics faced are important?

1 not important	2	3	4	5 very important

Did you feel free to express your opinions?

- Yes
- No
- Only in part
- No answer

How do you evaluate the organization of the event?

1 Not good	2	3	4	5 Very good

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Was the duration of the assembly appropriate?

- Too short
- Too long
- Adequate
- No answer

Do you think that this citizens' jury will have a concrete impact on future decisions?

- Yes
- No
- In part
- No answer

Are you interested in taking part in similar events in the future?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- No answer

If yes or maybe, which topics would you like to be faced in future citizens' juries?

What should be improved in the organization of such an event?

Other comments for the organizers:

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Thank you for your participation!

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d. CJs Position papers

CITIZENS' JURY (CJ) OF BOLZANO/BOZEN

1. Overview of the Citizen Jury	
<i>Title</i>	"Gestire le crisi presenti e future" / "Krisen bewältigen: Heute und in Zukunft"
<i>Date and location</i>	Bolzano/Bozen, 8 March 2025
<i>Local partner involved in the organization</i>	Eurac Research, Institute for Comparative Federalism Team: Greta Klotz and Chiara Salati
<i>Pilot municipality in numbers (inhabitants, size)</i>	106,357 inhabitants approximately. This represents 19.8% of the total population of South Tyrol (Source: https://www.autonomy-dashboard.info/it) 52.30 km ²
<i>Pilot municipality in max. 150 words: Briefly describe the territory and point out main characteristics.</i>	Bolzano is the capital of the autonomous province of Bolzano – South Tyrol and the seat of the provincial government. The Statute of Autonomy of South Tyrol recognizes three official linguistic groups: German, Italian, and Ladin. The educational system also follows the logic of separating the linguistic groups. The Provincial Council of South Tyrol, as the democratically elected central body, enacts the autonomous legislation of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano – South Tyrol. Regarding financial autonomy, about 90% of the taxes collected in South Tyrol are owed to the Autonomous Province of Bolzano – South Tyrol.
<i>Length</i>	8:30 – 14:00
<i>Number of participants (all names are listed in alphabetical order of family names)</i>	8 total participants. The group was heterogeneous in terms of gender and age. Level of education: 1 Bachelor's degree or equivalent; 4 Master's degrees or equivalent; 1 PhD; 2 Secondary school. Occupation: 1 Retired; 1 Job seeker; 3 Full-time employees; 1 Part-time employee; 2 Students.
<i>How were participants selected?</i>	The participants were selected through multiple methods: a) lottery, b) open online invitation, c) open paper-based invitation posted on noticeboards.

	<p>A) The lottery was the primary method used. It was carried out by the Municipality of Bolzano – in collaboration with which the event was organized – and specifically by the Office of Demographic Services using statistical software. Citizens were selected based on certain criteria: residence, gender, and legal age. Based on these criteria, the Municipality selected 120 names and sent them to the Eurac team, which took care of sending them the invitation letters.</p> <p>B) The open online invitation (open call) was the second method used, to supplement the lottery. Since we did not receive enough confirmations through the lottery, we decided to try to reach more people through this open invitation: it was published online on our website and circulated through various professional networks of Eurac, the Municipality, and personal contacts.</p> <p>C) Finally, the first two methods were supplemented by posting the paper version of the open invitation on various noticeboards throughout the city (about 15). In this way, the open invitation to participate reached noticeboards in libraries, theaters, museums, bars, sports centers, civic centers, and shops.</p>
<p><i>Facilitator (name and profession)</i></p>	<p>MMag. Greta Klotz (researcher, Eurac Research), Dr. Chiara Salati (researcher, Eurac Research).</p> <p>This was a replacement as the originally planned facilitator could not participate (Dr. Sonia Gantioler, researcher at Eurac Research).</p>
<p><i>Were there obstacles to the involvement of citizens in the event?</i></p>	<p>It was not easy to find/invite a large number of citizens, and we did not reach the goal of 15 citizens as planned. Therefore, we organized an open invitation in addition to the lottery conducted by the Municipality. The main obstacles were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The coincidence of many other events in Bolzano on the day of the citizens' assembly (e.g., International Women's Day): this led many interested people to decline the invitation. • Organizational difficulties in terms of estimating the numbers for the lottery. • Bureaucratic organizational difficulties that impacted the timing of the event (invitations might have been sent too late).
<p><i>How did the CJ take place? Into how many phases was the CJ structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).</i></p>	<p>The citizens' assembly was divided into several phases as follows:</p> <p>8:30-9:00 REGISTRATION AND PARTICIPANTS 9:00-9:20 WELCOME 9:20-9:40 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES 9:40-10:20 EXPERT PRESENTATIONS</p>

	<p>BREAK 10:30-12:00 DISCUSSION AND DEFINITION OF RECOMMENDATIONS 12:00-12:40 PLENARY SESSION 12:40-13:00 CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS</p> <p>However, this initial program was modified during the event, as the deliberation phase (discussion and definition of recommendations) was significantly extended on the spot because participants wished to discuss longer. The three experts provided input on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crisis and local participation • Crisis and risks • Crisis and local finance
<p><i>Which general considerations on the CJ to report?</i></p>	<p>In general, the event was a success. The presentations by the experts were very interesting and not too long (15 min each). The discussion among the citizens was very active. We separated the group of 8 into two small groups of 4 people to facilitate the discussion and guarantee that everybody would feel free to speak.</p> <p>We realized that we have planned too short a time for the deliberation phase. It would have been better to have more time dedicated to that phase.</p> <p>The phase of the presentation of the recommendations by the citizens and the feedback given by the experts and the political representative was also very useful for providing citizens with a response according to the theoretical context given by experts and the institutional activities of the municipality in line or not with the recommendations.</p>
<p><i>Which challenges did the CJ face?</i></p>	<p>The challenges (not necessarily negative) encountered during the event were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The time allocated for the discussion phase (deliberation) was too short: the citizens would have continued to discuss for a longer period. For future events, it would be useful to plan for a longer phase. • Citizens had difficulty at the beginning of the discussion phase when divided into groups. For future events, it is important to ensure that clear instructions are given so that the discussion can proceed more easily.
<p><i>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the CJ that should be pointed out?</i></p>	<p>Critical aspects that had a negative impact on the workload were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in finding participants: we did not reach 15 citizens. • Defining the number of invitations to send: we sent 120, but it would have been necessary to send more. • Collaboration with the municipal public offices: often many bureaucratic and logistical issues slowed down the process. • Role of the facilitator: it is necessary to prepare a plan B in case the facilitator is unable to participate at the last minute.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is essential to clearly define from the beginning the expected outcome and the follow-up to the citizens' work to avoid creating false expectations. • Difficulty in requesting concrete follow-up from the municipal administration due to the overlap with local elections (May 4).
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2. Deliberation phase

- *How did the deliberative phase take place?*
- *Which method did the facilitator follow?*

We followed an open discussion method; however, we separated the group of 8 into two small groups of 4. The deliberation phase was structured into four phases, where phases 1 and 4 were done as a group together, whereas phases 2 and 3 were in smaller groups:

1. **Brainstorming on crisis scenarios**
2. **Discussion**
3. **Drafting of recommendations**
4. **“Priority” voting on recommendations**

Phase 1. The first phase started with an open brainstorming on which crisis scenario the citizen would have liked to focus on, or which one would be interesting for them. They were asked to imagine Bolzano in 2030, and in specific to imagine a concrete crisis scenario involving citizens and having an impact on them. They wrote such scenarios on a post it, and it was clear that the majority among them chose a scenario connected to climate change and increasing temperatures.

Phase 2. They were divided into two groups of four participants each, and – before starting the discussion – they wrote down the precise crisis scenario they wanted to write recommendations on: group 1 decided to work on “RISING TEMPERATURE AND WATER SHORTAGE”, while group 2 on “HEATWAVES”. They started an active discussion on how the municipality or other institutional actors should react to this crisis, how to prevent it already now and which recommendations could be given them.

Phase 3. The two groups drafted the recommendations defining for each one the title, its target, a description and the motivation for that.

Phase 4. In phase 4 one speaker per group presented the recommendations to the plenum consisting of all participants, the three experts, organizers/facilitators and one political representative of Bolzano local government who arrived in the meantime. After the presentation, the 3 experts and the politician reacted to the recommendations with comments and feedback. At the end of that, citizens were asked to vote on the level of importance for them to be given to the recommendations: high importance (vote with a green paper), low importance (vote with a red paper), neutral stand (vote with a white paper).

3. Recommendations drafted

- *Which recommendations did citizens elaborate?*

The 8 citizens, divided into two groups of 4, developed a total of 10 recommendations.

Group 1 developed the following 6 recommendations:

1. Increase green areas (directed to the Municipality)
2. Increase restrictions on the circulation of cars (and motorcycles) (directed to the Municipality and Province)
3. Organize accessible drinking water points for all (directed to the Municipality)
4. Develop an emergency communication plan (directed to the Municipality)
5. Create water reserves (directed to the Province)
6. Organize climate shelters (directed to the Municipality)

Group 2 developed the following 4 recommendations:

7. Adapt the civil protection label to the city of Bolzano (directed to the Municipality and Civil Protection)
8. Adapt risk detection and the development of preventive measures by age groups and categories of the population (directed to the Municipality, Health Authority, social services, category representatives, and other municipalities)
9. Strengthen and expand the "thrilling summer" initiative for vulnerable categories and interested populations (directed to the Municipality, Social Services, Province)
10. Introduce specific heat countermeasures in the local urban planning plan (directed to the Municipality)

During the final plenary phase, the two groups presented their recommendations to each other. Since some were similar, they were consolidated during this plenary phase. Specifically:

- Recommendations 6 and 9 were combined into one: 11) Expand initiatives for green areas and public spaces (examples: "thrilling summer" initiative, climate shelters, etc.)
- Recommendations 1, 3, and 10 were combined into one: 12) Introduce specific heat countermeasures in the municipal urban planning plan (examples: increase green areas, install accessible drinking water points for all).

4. Debate and conflicting opinions

- *Which recommendations had conflicting opinions?*
- *On which recommendations was there agreement among the citizens?*

Debate: As the participants were divided into two groups, they discussed in smaller groups of 4 during the deliberative phase. This phase did not involve active participation from the facilitators in guiding the citizens' discussion: this allowed for more freedom of expression from the citizens, who greatly appreciated the time to discuss freely with each other. The discussion thus mainly took place among the citizens themselves. Nevertheless, the facilitators did move between the tables several times to answer questions and occasionally

to stimulate the discussion with the guiding questions presented during the team and expert presentation. These questions were also printed and distributed to the participants to encourage discussion. The experts were also available during this phase to answer any additional questions.

Agreed and conflicting opinions: Some emerged in the plenary debate, while others occurred during the group debate. It is not possible to report any conflicting opinions from the debate phase, as this was a time when the citizens discussed independently, without facilitation. During the plenary session, generally, there was agreement among all the citizens on the proposals. However, there was more agreement on some proposals and less on others.

We gathered preferences through a voting system with colored cards indicating high importance (green card), low importance (red card), or indifference (white card) for each recommendation. The results were as follows (the two recommendations 12 and 5 received unanimous consensus):

- Recommendation 7: Green 1; Red 2; White 5.
- Recommendation 8: Green 7; Red 0; White 1.
- Recommendation 11: Green 6; Red 1; White 1.
- **Recommendation 12: Green 8; Red 0; White 0.**
- Recommendation 2: Green 5; Red 1; White 2.
- Recommendation 4: Green 3; Red 1; White 4.
- **Recommendation 5: Green 8; Red 0; White 0.**

One particular issue raised conflicting opinions: the functioning of public transportation in Bolzano (during the discussion on recommendation 2). Some argued that the system works well, while others mentioned delays, a limited number of bus runs, and a lack of routes. These perceptions likely depend on several factors. In summary, however, it seems that it would be very useful for the Municipality to carry out an updated study on the actual needs and usage of transportation services.

5. Suggestions for the future

- *Which lessons to learn for the organization of future citizens' juries, which suggestions?*

Two are the main suggestions for organizing similar events in the future:

- Longer time for the deliberation phase.
- Ensure the involvement of the municipality in the follow-up: the Municipality must commit to at least listening to/receiving the recommendations (possibly also allowing them to be presented by the citizens, and not just by the organizers) so as not to frustrate the citizens' expectations. The optimal scenario would be for the Municipality to engage in a specific dialogue with the citizens about these recommendations, explaining which ones can have institutional follow-up and which ones cannot, and providing adequate reasoning so that the citizens can understand the Municipality's decisions on how to proceed. This should be done with the awareness that, in any case, these recommendations are not binding but are purely consultative.

6. Feedback from citizens

- *What feedback did citizens report in their evaluation forms? (summary)*

The overall feedback from the citizens was very positive. Seven out of eight participants rated the event with the two highest evaluation scores, while only one gave a neutral rating. The majority of participants also stated that their expectations were met (5 out of 8). Additionally, all participants agreed that the topics discussed were highly important, and seven out of eight expressed interests in attending similar events in the future. Furthermore, all participants felt free to share their opinions during the discussions.

The aspects participants appreciated the most were the exchange and discussions among people (5). Other positive comments included the logistics and the expert input. As for areas of criticism, the main point was the timing (3 responses): two participants felt the event was too short, while one felt it was too long. Another point raised was the desire for more information in advance about what the municipality is doing.

Regarding whether the participants believe their recommendations will have concrete outcomes, the feedback was confident: half of the group answered "yes," while the other half responded "in part."

Regarding the organization and time planning, separate questions were asked. The event's overall organization received high praise from all participants, while opinions about the timing were divided. For half of the group, the timing was adequate, while three participants felt it was too short, and one felt it was too long.

Finally, participants provided feedback on the event's organization. Three individuals again mentioned that the duration was too short. Other suggestions included: the Saturday morning date, falling within a holiday period, was not ideal; more short presentations by local politicians would have been appreciated; and a more detailed, step-by-step communication process would have been helpful.

CITIZENS' JURY (CJ) OF HULDENBERG

1. Overview of the Citizen Jury	
<i>Title</i>	<p>“Burgerpanel UAntwerpen x Huldenberg: vertrouwen en communicatie in tijden van crisis”</p> <p>“Citizen jury UAntwerp x Huldenberg: trust and communication in times of crisis”</p>
<i>Date and location</i>	Huldenberg, 29 March 2025, 13u30-17u
<i>Local partner involved in the organization</i>	<p>University of Antwerp</p> <p>Team composed of: Jakob Frateur, Peter Bursens, Patricia Popelier and Loes Reijnders</p>
<i>Pilot municipality in numbers (inhabitants, size)</i>	Huldenberg: 10.083 inhabitants; 39,64km ²
Pilot municipality in max. 150 words: Briefly describe the territory and point out main characteristics.	Huldenberg is a rural municipality in the province of Flemish Brabant (Flanders) with 10.083 residents (Stadsmonitor Vlaanderen 2024). In addition to Huldenberg itself, the municipality also includes the sub-municipalities of Loonbeek, Neerijse, Ottenburg and Sint-Agatha-Rode. The municipality borders the Walloon region.
Number of participants	5
How were participants selected?	First, the event was announced in the municipal gazette and through public posts on social media of the municipal account. The municipality also send direct invitations to citizens who are part of the ‘participation-database’ of the municipality of Huldenberg.
Facilitator (name and profession)	Wim Van Roy, coordinator from De Wakkere Burger, non-profit organisation with a focus on citizen participation and deliberative democracy.
Were there obstacles to the involvement of citizens in the event?	The main obstacle was a lack of response, with only 5 citizens signing up for the event. However, this did allow for a more in-depth discussion with the present citizens.
How did the CJ take place? Into how many phases was the CJ structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).	<p>The Citizen Jury took place over one afternoon, in person on Saturday the 29th of March. The meeting was in person and took place in a conference room of the town hall of Huldenberg. There were two phases of citizen involvement.</p> <p>Planning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction LEGITIMULT project and project findings

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First deliberation phase: general cases and questions based on the research on trust in WP5 of the LEGITIMULT project. - Break - Second deliberation phase: Cases and questions from the municipality of Huldenberg - Formulating recommendations and conclusion
<p>Which general considerations on the CJ to report?</p>	<p>Not only is it important to note that we only had 5 participants, which makes the opinions of the group less democratically representative, most of the participants were also experienced professionally with public functions and service or experience with crisis-management. Only one of the participants did not identify as having specific personal experience with the topic.</p> <p>Due to the location of Huldenberg, bordering the Walloon region, the respondents also occasionally voiced certain opinions with this as the main argument. Since it so close to the regional language border, they sometimes noticed large differences between regional rules and policy and often referred to the importance of interregional coordination. This sentiment might be less strong in other geographical regions.</p>
<p>Which challenges did the CJ face?</p>	<p>There were no strong challenges during the process. Because the group was relatively small (5) and well moderated, all citizens participated actively and were able to voice their opinion in all of the cases and questions. On one or two occasions the conversation was drifting slightly (e.g., case D: cloud of gas, participants started talking about whether or not rules would be mandatory instead of which level of government should be in charge), and on one other occasion the coordinator had to cut the conversation off to move on to the next question as the conversation was getting too lengthy. Overall, however, participants were involved and could voice their opinion in an open setting, which they evaluated as a positive.</p>
<p>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the CJ that should be pointed out?</p>	<p>Two participants voiced they would have preferred the Citizen Jury took place on a weekday, and that this might have led to a higher response rate. Other than that, the organization and format were perceived positively.</p>

2. Deliberation phase

- How did the deliberative phase take place?

The deliberation used cases as examples. First, the focus was not related to Huldernberg, but more in general, with the example of another disease outbreak (similar to COVID). The questions were about which level of government would be most trusted in times of crisis, whether it was preferred levels of government would discuss amongst each other before making a decision on protective or economic compensation measures in times of crisis, and which principles are most important to the individual participants.

After this, results from the LEGITIMULT project were shared.

Lastly, the participants went over questions and cases specific to hypothetical crises in Huldernberg: critical voices on governments, which communication they prefer from the municipality in times of crisis, which level they prefer to communicate, and the cases: What the municipality should keep open in times of crisis, how to communicate local evacuation, what to do after a data breach, and which level of government citizens prefer to communicate in case of a gas cloud.

- Which method did the facilitator follow?

Given that it was a smaller group, discussions were held in plenum with the facilitator making sure that each participant could voice its opinion. From the discussions, the moderator distilled a common position that was either accepted by the participants, or further discussed and refined until a common understanding was reached.

3. Recommendations drafted

- Which recommendations did citizens elaborate?

First deliberation phase.

When it comes to making decisions and communicating in times of crisis: Participants did not like big differences in rules between regions, meaning the main rules should be mandated from the country or even the European level. However, communication and finetuning can be done by the local (and regional) level.

Following the first recommendation, citizens' value intergovernmental cooperation, especially as the crisis lingers on. They agreed that, in the first phases, strong and swift reactions might be necessary, so the federal levels can unilaterally decide. However, the subnational levels, and especially the local level, should be increasingly involved in crisis management and implementation of measures during the crisis.

Legality and transparency are important crisis management values. Both need to be adhered to when managing a crisis. Regarding transparency specifically, the reason behind measures and the (scientific) grounds for them should be explicated.

Second deliberation phase: The CJ also discussed - in collaboration with the municipality - issues of crisis communication, which led to the elaboration of recommendations on further points.

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Emergency plan: An emergency plan had to be in place, which should be well thought out ahead of time and with the necessary expertise. This can guarantee a fast response where needed. An evacuation plan was an important part of this emergency plan, and it is important that the rights of citizens are not violated.

Communication in times of crisis: It was not clear for all citizens how they currently receive information. They want more clarity on this, such as a reminder to sign up for BE-alert or a separate Huldenberg alert. Not all have access to social media, so perhaps news could also be shared on the municipality website, and it can be mentioned that news can be found here through local signs or a local paper. However, it should be noted that a BE-alert or a new Huldenberg alert should only be used in situations of a certain severity.

Services that should remain available in times of crisis: The identity card should always remain available to get replaced or requested, as this is the main communication and access to government services.

In case of a data breach: In the case of a data breach it is the municipality’s responsibility to make sure citizens are informed of what information of them is possibly shared, which risks are involved in this, and whether there is action required from the citizen. This needs to be explained clearly and easily understandable. Data breaches or hacks can happen, but it is the municipality’s responsibility to inform the citizens, solve it where possible, and follow up.

4. Debate and conflicting opinions

- Which recommendations had conflicting opinions?

First deliberation phase.

Level of government in times of crisis: Two of the participants voiced to have the most trust in the regional level, because this level is closest to the citizens and can fine tune depending on the needs of their region. Two others believed the federal level would be the best, which was argued by the fact that they live close to the border of Wallonia and noticed large differences in rules between regions. They also believed the local level would not have the needed expertise to make informed decisions. One citizen believed the European level to be the most effective to make decisions because they have the most expertise and direct contact with science. The participants were able to reach a middle ground where there are no big differences between regions, with the main big rules being mandated from the country or European level, while communication and finetuning can be done by the local level.

Level of communication between layers of government in times of crisis: While three citizens immediately voiced the need for a top-down decision from one person in charge, in order to guarantee a fast response, two others were more hesitant. The main person responsible was assumed to be the mayor. The two hesitant participants voiced that a mayor would not have the necessary expertise, and possibly not even the legal rights to make such decisions. There was also fear of possible abuse of power. Eventually a middle ground was found, where the participants agreed an emergency plan had to be in place, which is well though out ahead of time and with the

necessary expertise. This can guarantee a fast response where needed. An evacuation plan was an important part of this emergency plan, and it is important that the rights of citizens are not violated.

Priorities of principles in times of crisis: There were varying opinions on which principles were most important. While three participants agreed that legality was one of their top priorities, another thought it was the least important. Three citizens believed proportionality to be one of the most important. Two others believed transparency to be the most important, so citizens understand why rules are there. This led to a discussion on what can be described as transparency, as a certain level of transparency (specifically in times of uncertainty) might lead to panic. Some of the citizens believed a government should be as transparent as possible, including possibly voicing that they are not in control anymore, while others believed the government should mainly seem in control and does not need to share details.

Second deliberation phase.

Emergency plan: Although all citizens agreed that Huldenberg should have an emergency plan (and evacuation plan) in place, there was disagreement on whether this plan should be communicated to citizens before a crisis (e.g., now) or wait until there is a crisis. Some participants believed upfront communication might cause unnecessary disorganization. Others did believe it needed to be communicated upfront, so people would know what to do and the municipality is transparent. There was agreement that BE-alert would be suitable for this, but in addition to local initiatives (use of the local signs, possibly driving around with a message) for people who are not signed up for BE-alert.

Gas cloud close to city: In the hypothetical scenario of a gas cloud, some participants voiced their only priority is a quick and clear plan, and it does not matter which level of government decides it. Others said that they might not take the advice, specifically related to gardens and produce, either way, so the main priority is that it is not a mandatory plan. One voiced they would prefer a local government worker to provide advice, while two others voiced they preferred the federal/national level to make decisions based on expertise.

- On which recommendations was there agreement among the citizens?

First deliberation phase.

Critical voices on the government: All participants agreed that hearing critical voices and contradicting opinions strengthened did not damage their trust in government. They believed that the fact that the government or media did not suppress these voices and opinions was sign of a healthy democratic government people are allowed to criticize. It is also expected, once a crisis lasts longer (such as COVID), critical voices start to emerge more. They also agreed that critique of certain actors (judges, experts...) has more impact on their trust, rather negatively, than the critique of other actors (politicians, citizens).

Second deliberation phase.

Sharing of information in Huldenberg: All the participants agreed that the current way information is shared is sub-optimal. There is a new sign where the city can share information, but other than that it was not clear for some of them how they received information. Some received it through social media, which was agreed that it

should not be the only channels as not everyone has access to this, while others are signed up for BE-alert. There was agreement that there should be more clarity in this, with maybe residents being notified that they can/should sign up for BE-alert or making a separate Huldenberg alert. It was also noted that this should only be used in a serious situation. Recently there were problems with a water pipe, which gave them a notification, which was deemed unnecessary.

There was also agreement on which services should remain available in times of crisis: The identity card should be able to be replaced or requested from the municipality. This was considered the most relevant and urgent service from the city and should therefore always remain accessible. The municipality also needs to remain accessible, either online, or when internet is (temporarily) unavailable by phone.

Data breach: Participants agreed that in the case of a data breach it is the municipality's responsibility to make sure citizens are informed of what information of them is possibly shared, which risks are involved in this, and whether there is action required from the citizen. This needs to be explained clearly and easily understandable. Data breaches or hacks can happen, but it is the municipality's responsibility to inform the citizens, solve it where possible, and follow up.

5. Suggestions for the future

- Which lessons to learn for the organization of future citizens' juries, which suggestions?

The organization was seen as very positive by the participants: The use of cases and open-ended questions left a lot of room for discussions. However, it should be mentioned that most of the citizens involved had more prior experience than the average citizen with this topic.

The Citizen Jury took place on a Saturday afternoon, close to the citizens (town hall of Huldenberg). It lasted about 4 hours, which was evaluated by most participants to be the correct length. One citizen did say it lasted too long. Two other mentioned they would have preferred it if the Citizen Jury took place on a weekday.

They also suggested possible topics for future citizen involvement: safety, democracy, privacy protection, and a specific emergency plan.

6. Feedbacks from citizens

Organization and format: All involved citizens evaluated the Citizen Jury positively. One citizen mentioned the panel was too long, the others thought it was the right length (about 4 hours). Two citizens did mention they would have preferred it to take place on a weekday.

Results: Two citizens believe the results to have a concrete impact, while two others believe it would partially have an impact. One citizen decided to withhold from answering this question. There was also a comment that indicated the wish to have the results or impact communicated, possible through the regional paper of the municipality.

Three out of five participants wished to participate again in the future, while two answered maybe. The suggested topics for future citizen involvement are safety, democracy, privacy protection, and a specific emergency plan.

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CITIZENS' JURY (CJ) OF IZOLA/ISOLA

1. Overview of the Citizen Jury	
<i>Title</i>	Citizens' Assembly/CITIZENS' JURY (CJ) on legitimate crisis management at all decision-making levels (LEGITIMULT - Legitimate Crisis Governance in Multilevel Systems) and proposals for future crisis situations.
<i>Date and location</i>	Izola/Isola, 22 March 2025 10.00 -15:00 (10 am – 3 pm)
<i>Local partner involved in the organization</i>	The Institute for Ethnic Studies organized this CJ in cooperation with the Municipality of Izola/Isola.
<i>Pilot municipality in numbers (inhabitants, size)</i>	Commune of Izola/Isola, around 16.000 inhabitants, covers an area of 29 km ² .
<i>Pilot municipality in max. 150 words: Briefly describe the territory and point out main characteristics.</i>	<p>Izola/Isola is a lively mediterranean town, nowadays primarily a tourist center, yet it still preserves its heritage in fishing, as well as wine and olive oil production, which sets it apart from other coastal towns in the region. The Municipality of Izola/Isola is located in the southwestern part of the Republic of Slovenia and is part of the Coastal-Karst region. Marina Izola, with its 700 berths, offers an excellent starting point for cruising along the Adriatic coast.</p> <p>Izola's identity is shaped by the coexistence of two nations, their different languages, and a shared love for their homeland. The Self-Governing Community of the Italian Nationality in Izola/Isola is a public legal entity and an integral part of local autonomy.</p> <p>The town's rich and diverse architectural heritage, the mysterious alleys of the old town center, and the imposing stone portals bear witness to its turbulent history. The pulse of cultural events and celebrations, fishing traditions, entertainment, and sports activities all form an essential part of the area's cultural landscape.</p>
<i>Number of participants (all names are listed in alphabetical order of family names)</i>	11 inhabitants (see the list of participants) and the IES team composed of researchers: Dr. Danijel Grafenauer, Dr. Lara Sorgo, Dr. Sofija Zver and Prof. Dr. Mitja Žagar.
<i>How were participants selected?</i>	A public notice for participation in a civic discussion was published on the website of the Municipality of Izola/Isola, while the invitation was published also by some local/regional media (particularly local radio).
<i>Facilitator (name and profession)</i>	Dr. Lara Sorgo (social linguist) and Prof. Dr. Mitja Žagar (jurist and political scientist), both IES researchers.

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<p><i>Were there obstacles to the involvement of citizens in the event?</i></p>	<p>In accordance with the national legislation and decision of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Slovenia, electoral roll cannot be used for any other purpose. Consequently, a public notice for participation in a citizens' jury was published on the official website of the Municipality of Izola/Isola and their Facebook pages. Additionally, the information on the event was presented by some local media. After that, we had to wait for applications from interested citizens. A total of 11 citizens applied.</p>
<p><i>How did the CJ take place? Into how many phases was the CJ structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).</i></p>	<p>The CJ took place in the premises of the Manzioli Palace, located at Manzioli Square 5 in Izola/Isola, in the beautiful setting of the historical palace.</p> <p>We divided the citizens' jury into two content-related and temporally separate parts. In the first part, led by IES, the topic of the discussion was the Covid-19 pandemic management, in order to identify the key aspects of its societal management.</p> <p>In the second part, we attempted to identify what type of crisis scenarios could potentially occur in the Municipality of Izola/Isola in the future and what protocols should be applied in such situation situations.</p> <p>Workshop was organized as an open discussion between all participants, based upon the following agenda:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction: presentation of LEGITIMULT and CJ. • Introductory remarks by participants on crisis-related events, experiences, reflections, and assessments of Covid-19 crisis management by both the media and public authorities at the national, regional, and municipal levels. • Deliberative phase where citizens had the chance to express their opinions regarding the justification, proportionality, effectiveness, legality, and legitimacy of how the crisis was managed and its related measures. This deliberative phase aimed at stimulating participants to come up with recommendations on how crisis management and measures could be improved, and how to ensure their proportionality, effectiveness, and legitimacy in future crisis situations (e.g., epidemics/pandemics, natural and other disasters such as floods, fires, industrial accidents, etc.). • Key lessons learnt and recommendations • Conclusion
<p><i>Which general considerations on the CJ to report?</i></p>	<p>In the future, it is essential to include certain groups of people and their representatives in crisis management processes in order to ensure greater legitimacy of the measures eventually taken by public authorities. This was explicitly highlighted during the civic discussion. There is a need for better, more transparent, and fact-based communication. It was also emphasized that joint public services (e.g., healthcare, firefighters, civil protection, and the corresponding infrastructure) are necessary to enable more effective and</p>

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	appropriate responses to future crises. It lies in the responsibility of the state to provide and maintain these infrastructures. They believed that good communication, a well-organized information system, and high-quality public media are especially important.
<i>Which challenges did the CJ face?</i>	During the event, the main challenge we can report was the surge in the deliberative phase of so-called conspiracy theories. This can be seen as a reflection of current times. Nevertheless, they did not dominate the deliberation.
<i>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the CJ that should be pointed out?</i>	Concerning the organization of the event itself, the biggest difficulty we have encountered was citizen registration for the citizens' jury. With dedicated effort and the support of the Municipality of Izola/Isola and local media, we managed to secure in total 11 participants, which at the end granted a positive deliberation exercise. However, we can with no doubt report citizens' engagement in this deliberative event as a very critical aspect.

2. Deliberation phase

- *How did the deliberative phase take place?*
- *Which method did the facilitator follow?*

During the deliberative phase participants shared personal experiences, reflections, and their assessments of crisis management and measures taken, as well as the impacts and consequences of such measures during the Covid-19 pandemic at the national, regional, and municipal levels. Citizens were invited to discuss, in specific, the justification, proportionality, effectiveness, legality, and legitimacy of crisis management and related measures. The guiding questions looked at recommendations on how crisis management and measures could be improved, and how to ensure their proportionality, effectiveness, and legitimacy in future crisis situations (e.g., epidemics/pandemics, natural and other disasters such as floods, fires, industrial accidents, etc.).

Citizens also discussed the extent to which citizens and experts should be involved in crisis management processes and in the design, adoption, implementation, and evaluation (comprehensive assessment) of individual crisis measures. When, where, and how could they be included?

Based on the discussion, we recorded several examples of possible good and bad practices, along with the citizens' reflections, assessments, and suggestions for improving crisis management.

The facilitators followed the method of open and inclusive dialogue.

3. Recommendations drafted

- *Which recommendations did citizens elaborate?*

First: **on higher involvement and visibility of professionals in crisis management.**

Citizens pointed out that, when established protocols for handling such crises are in place, experts—not others—should be the ones leading the overall and societal response. Despite the previously mentioned distrust toward certain parts of the expert community, citizens believed that in cases such as natural disasters, it should be professionals and specialized services—many of which (e.g., civil protection, firefighters, etc.) enjoy a high level of respect in society (as confirmed by the citizens themselves)—who take the lead. In fact, all the participants agreed that, during crisis situations, common public services such as civil protection, public hospitals, firefighters, and others play a crucial role. They believed that it is necessary—both at the national and local levels—to maintain and further develop this essential infrastructure that can be key to an effective response and coordinated action in such critical moments.

Second: **on a better-defined division of roles between central and local authorities.**

The competences of central authorities and local government should be clearly defined, although it might be expected that also in the future national and/or global crises the central authorities would have the lead role—at least initially. They strongly expressed the need for clearly defined protocols for handling such and similar crises in the future. The aim would be to ensure a clearer and more structured response, avoiding the confusion and uncertainty that often occurred during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Third: **on a more fact-based communication of measures, and wider consultation on them.**

Citizens during the deliberation phase proposed that future communication about planned measures must be based on facts. They believed that such measures should be proportionate, effective, and adopted through consultations with a broader group of people and experts. Almost all participants emphasized inconsistent communication and a general lack of communication during the management of the Covid-19 crisis. They emphasized the importance of clear communication and a well-organized system of public information, supported by quality public media. In times of crisis, collaboration between experts, political leaders, public media, and services that assist people during such events is essential.

Fourth: **on the need to better tackle corruption in public procurement processes during a crisis.**

The discussion also highlighted the issue of corruption in the procurement of protective equipment, which, according to participants, must be eliminated in the future.

4. Debate and conflicting opinions

- *Which recommendations had conflicting opinions?*
- *On which recommendations was there agreement among the citizens?*

Citizens pointed out several issues related to the implementation of protocols for managing similar crises, notably the absence of such protocols, and the inconsistency in introducing measures to contain the Covid-19 pandemic.

They also criticized the interference of political decision-makers and politicians in the decisions of the medical profession (e.g., epidemiologists, infectious disease specialists, etc.). Some participants leaned towards conspiracy theories, claiming that the entire situation had been pre-planned for the profit of a few wealthy individuals.

Concerns were also raised about problems and potential corruption in the procurement of equipment for controlling the virus spread—such as face masks, respirators, disinfectants, and other supplies.

Some participants expressed the view that the public media and the expert community did not fulfill their roles adequately and gave in to the pressure of politicians and medical lobbies.

All in all, the deliberative phase revealed essentially one consideration: that citizens no longer trust the authorities or even the medical experts to the same extent as they did before the pandemic. This is due to many reasons: first, the frequent changes in measures to contain the Covid-19 pandemic. Second, the inconsistencies in their enforcement. Third, the issues faced in Slovenia with the functioning of the National Institute of Public Health – NIJZ, such as the removal of leadership and their replacement with individuals more aligned with the then-government. Fourth, the frequent absence of at least part of the expert community in explaining and justifying the necessity of specific measures.

5. Suggestions for the future

- *Which lessons to learn for the organization of future citizens' juries, which suggestions?*

From the organizational perspective of a future citizens' jury, these are the considerations that we could share:

- Concerning the difficulty to recruit participants: a possible solution could be to use a mix of personal invitations, local community organizations, and digital platforms to broaden reach.
- Concerning the willingness of participants to know more about the project in advance: a possible solution could be to send materials in advance (short videos, infographics, easy-to-read documents) or hold brief online or in-person session before the event begins
- Concerning the structure of the citizens' jury: we realized that a more structured process and clear workshop phases would have been very helpful, although overall the process was mostly smooth. In specific, the phases of gathering opinions, deliberation, recommendations writing would have benefitted if they were more clearly separated and balanced in terms of time.
- Concerning the inclusion of diverse voices: the workshop effectively highlighted the importance of involving different social groups. In the future, it would be beneficial to ensure even greater diversity among participants (in terms of age, language, region, social background) to make the conclusions more representative.
- Concerning participants' expectations to "be listened to": one of the key positive aspects was that participants felt heard. For the future, creating such moments of discussion for equal expression is a crucial condition for successful deliberation.
- Concerning the potential for learning and empowerment: the process was also an opportunity for learning – about crisis management, the role of institutions, and participatory methods. In the future, it

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would be worthwhile to include brief introductory trainings or presentations to make the discussion even more informed.

6. Feedback from citizens

- *What feedback did citizens report in their evaluation forms? (summary)*

The participants during the citizens' jury evaluated the event and its implementation very positively. After the event, they expressed appreciation for the diversity of opinions, testimonies, and experiences that they had the chance to exchange, as well as for the opportunity to confront and exchange views in an open, public, and inclusive dialogue. They felt that they were able to freely express their opinions.

The event was, in their view, of appropriate duration and well-structured.

They believed—and expressed hope—that similar events could have an influence on future decision-making in the context of various crises and beyond. They felt that the key recommendations adopted during such discussions could contribute to more effective management of future crises and pandemics.

The topic was considered highly relevant, especially given the likelihood of similar events or crisis situations occurring in the future. They also highlighted the excellent facilitation of the civic discussion by the experts.

Participants suggested that future civic discussions could also address topics such as environmental protection, housing policy, cybersecurity, the spread of misinformation, mass tourism, and water resources in the municipality.

They also noted that similar events would benefit from greater public visibility. They suggested announcing them in public media and possibly introducing a live stream for future civic discussions, as this could engage a wider audience.

POSITION PAPER CITIZENS' JURY (CJ) BERGEN

1. Overview of the Citizen Jury	
<i>Title</i>	Facing present and future crises [<i>Møter nåværende og fremtidige kriser</i>]
<i>Date and location</i>	Saturday 23 August 2025, 10.00-15.30 i Bergen kommune. (Teatersalen, Manufakturhuset, Peter Motzfeldts gate 2, 5016 Bergen)
<i>Local partner involved in the organization</i>	Andreas Roaldsnes (senior advisor) was the local contact person of Bergen municipality [<i>Bergen kommune</i>]. Roaldsnes has a PhD from the Department of Information Science and Media Studies at the University of Bergen. William Hazell (section manager) approved the citizen jury and organized the presence of a politician from the city council. Arjan H. Schakel (organizer and expert), Sveinung Arnesen (moderator), and Alexander Verdoes (facilitator) were involved on behalf of the University of Bergen (the Department of Government and the Department of Comparative Politics) and Francisco Javier Romero Caro (organizer and expert) was involved on behalf of Eurac Research (Bolzano Bozen, Italy). Bergen municipality was eager to facilitate this citizen jury. The City of Bergen has experience with facilitating citizen jury's and focus groups, and highly values the soliciting of citizens' perceptions and viewpoints.
<i>Pilot municipality in numbers (inhabitants, size)</i>	Bergen municipality has 294,029 inhabitants (on 1 January 2025) and the city's total area is 465.3km ² .
<i>Pilot municipality in max. 150 words: Briefly describe the territory and point out main characteristics.</i>	Bergen is a city with historical roots going back to Viking times and was founded by King Olav Kyrre in 1070. Up until today, Bergen has been a commercial and cultural center, and the municipality is the second largest city in the country (in population size). Bergen lies in the county [<i>fylkeskommune</i>] of Vestland but was a county of its own until 1972.
<i>Number of participants</i>	18 participants participated in the citizen jury. This is a relatively high number. An explanation can be that the selected citizens received an invitation letter on Bergen municipality paper, signed by a politician (Reidar Digranes) who is sitting in the city council for industry, culture and sports [<i>byråd for næring, kultur of idrett</i>]. In addition, the invitation letter was sent via e-mail through a digital channel that Bergen municipality (and

	<p>other government organizations) use to communicate with citizens (Digipost: https://www.digipost.no/en).</p>
<p><i>How were participants selected?</i></p>	<p>Bergen municipality was responsible for randomly drawing a pool of 800 citizens who were selected through a stratified sample based on neighbourhood, gender, and age. These 800 citizens received an invitation letter signed by Bergen municipality (Reidar Driganes) and the University of Bergen (Arjan Schakel). The invitation letter mentioned that the citizen was randomly selected by Bergen municipality to participate in a citizen jury on how Bergen municipality should handle a possible future crisis.</p>
<p><i>Facilitator (name and profession)</i></p>	<p>Sveinung Arnesen facilitated the deliberation phase. The organizers of the citizen jury (Arjan Schakel, Francisco Javier Romero Caro, and Alexander Verdoes) are non-native Norwegian speakers. To ensure that the citizens could fully understand the tasks assigned to them, we wanted to have a colleague involved who is a native Norwegian speaker and who has experience with the organization of citizen jury's. Sveinung Arnesen is Research Professor at NORCE and Professor at the Department of Government at the University of Bergen and he has extensive research experience on democratic innovation and legitimate decision-making including deliberative polls and citizen jury's.</p>

<p><i>Were there obstacles to the involvement of citizens in the event?</i></p>	<p>An invitation letter was sent to 800 randomly selected citizens. The invitation letter asked citizens to send an e-mail to Arjan Schakel to confirm their participation in the citizen jury before 20 August 2025. A total of 74 reactions (9,25%) were received: 32 citizens declined the invitation (4,0%), 21 participants were invited (2,6%), but 18 citizens (2,25%) participated in the citizen jury, and 3 citizens (0,4%) wanted to participate but had to be refused because the citizen jury could not have more than 20 participants (for logistical and organizational reasons). Overall, one may conclude that the response and participation rates were relatively high. We ascribe this to the four factors: the invitation letter was (1) printed on official Bergen municipality paper; (2) sent from Bergen municipality; (3) signed by a municipal politician; (4) and distributed through a digital channel through which citizens receive official and important post from various governmental and non-governmental organizations. The invitation letter was sent via Fiks melding (https://ksdigital.no/tjenestene/fiks-melding/), which utilizes Digipost, and the random selection of 800 citizens was drawn from the National Population Registry (<i>Folkeregisteret</i>). Selected citizens who have opted out of digital communications received their invitation by post.</p>
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<p><i>How did the CJ take place? Into how many phases was the CJ structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).</i></p>	<p>The citizen jury’s duration was 5.5 hours starting at 10.00 and concluding at 15.30 (the schedule is provided below). There was a half hour lunch between 12.30-13.00. Between 9.45-10.15, citizens were individually welcomed as they arrived and guided to a table where they were asked to register on the participant list, to sign two consent forms, and to complete a short survey. Meanwhile they could get a coffee, tea or juice and they found a place at a table which was placed in a large U-shape. The welcome, introduction and expert presentations started at 10.15 instead of 10.30 because all citizens arrived early.</p> <p>The introduction included a short round of introductions from the citizens during which citizens mentioned their names and they could tell something about their expectations and reasons for attending the citizen jury. A number of citizens mentioned that they found the topic interesting, both from a personal interest but also from a professional interest (working with young people and in the health sector). Other citizens were curious to learn what was done during the Covid-19 crisis and some citizens were eager to contribute to the group based on their experiences. After the round of introductions, the participants were informed about the LEGITIMULT project, the ‘method’ of citizen jury’s, and the purpose of the citizen jury, i.e. drafting of recommendations to be presented to Bergen municipality and the European Commission as non-binding advice (Francisco Javier Romero Caro).</p> <p>The first expert input focused on types of crises, the types of risks involved, and which impacts and factors (cooperation/coordination, trust, communication) could/should be considered (Francisco Javier Romero Caro).</p> <p>The second expert input (Arjan Schakel) focused on the Covid-19 crisis in</p>
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	<p>Norway and explained that most crisis measures are impactful because they often restrict or limit fundamental freedoms and rights. The participants were subsequently introduced with governance dilemmas (reducing the further spread of an infectious disease versus the interests of the people involved affected by a restriction) and a crucial governance question (explaining that there are drawbacks and benefits when municipalities, the national government, or both decide on restrictions) which were all illustrated and explained by several examples from Norway.</p> <p>The welcome, introduction, and expert inputs lasted for about an hour and were followed by two deliberation phases (between 11.30-12.30 and between 13.10 and 14.30) and a plenary during which citizens voted on the recommendations (between 14.45-15.15) which are discussed in detail below. The lunch lasted a bit longer because Reidar Digranes, the politician from Bergen municipality who co-signed the invitation letter, came by to hold a short speech and to take a photo. The citizen jury ended with a short conclusion (between 15.15-15.30) during which citizens were thanked, were reminded that their recommendations will be presented to Bergen municipality and the European Commission as non-binding advice, were asked to complete the evaluation form, and were invited to collect their gift bag.</p>
<p><i>Which general considerations on the CJ to report?</i></p>	<p>Due to the size of the citizen jury (18 participants) we were concerned that it would be difficult to enable all citizens to contribute to the deliberations. We decided to split-up the groups of 18 participants into two groups of four and two groups of five citizens who were given the same tasks.</p>

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<p><i>Which challenges did the CJ face?</i></p>	<p>The citizen jury ran very smoothly and did not face any major challenges. This can be ascribed to two main factors. First, the participating citizens took the citizen jury very seriously, they were very attentive listeners to the expert inputs, and they showed a remarkable ability to work independently during the deliberation phases. Second, the organizers and facilitators communicated very well with each other and were flexible to adapt the organization of the citizen jury to unforeseen circumstances and wishes. The following example illustrates both factors. The room in which the first part of the citizen jury took place (10.00-11.30) had an echo, sounds were mingled when several people talked at the same time, and the air was warm and without oxygen. There were other smaller rooms in the vicinity, and instead of breaking down the tables out from the U-shape pattern to form four groups within the common room, the subgroups of citizens were allocated their own room, and one sub-group decided to sit outside. A challenge could have been not having sufficient time to address questions and unclarities or to help or facilitate the deliberations, but all four sub-groups showed an extraordinary ability to work independently. The moderator (Sveinung Arnesen) and the principal organizer (Arjan Schakel) made several rounds during the deliberations, but there were very few questions, and it was quite clear that they had to restrict their rounds to two times per deliberation phase in order to avoid too much ‘intrusion’ in a group’s deliberation and work.</p>
<p><i>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the CJ that should be pointed out?</i></p>	<p>Because the moderator and principal organizer did not (and should have not) go by the four sub-groups during the deliberation phases, we cannot report much on how the various sub-group deliberations went. But all citizens appeared to be engaged, they made their own remarks and observations on their own paper before filling in the forms they were given, and we observed that all citizens contributed to the deliberations within a sub-group.</p>

2. Deliberation phase

- *How did the deliberative phase take place?*

There were two deliberation phases. During the first deliberation phase (11.30-12.30), the sub-groups were asked to choose two to three 'guiding questions' that were used for the drafting of two to four recommendation during the second deliberation phase (13.20-14.30). The welcome, introduction, and expert inputs were in English, but the deliberation phases were held in Norwegian and the citizens deliberated in Norwegian. All consent forms, surveys, and handed-out forms (including the guidance question and the recommendations forms) were provided in Norwegian and in English.

- *Which method did the facilitator follow?*

The citizens were first introduced to the following hypothetical situation which was explained by the principal organizer (Arjan Schakel) who also provided some additional context (e.g. the legal obligation for Norwegian municipalities to have an emergency preparedness plan):

Imagine the municipality of Bergen is drafting an emergency preparedness plan. The document will include a proposed action plan in case an epidemic will occur. Bergen municipality has asked you to provide recommendations on what to include in the proposed action plan based on your experience of the Covid-19 crisis.

The participants were divided into four sub-groups which received the task to select two or three guidance questions which they would like to focus on in the second phase of their deliberations during which they developed recommendations. The number of times a guidance question was selected by a sub-group is indicated in between the brackets.

1. *How could citizen participation help Bergen municipality in managing a future epidemic? [1x]*
2. *Should citizens be involved during the management of an epidemic? If yes, how can or should this be organized? [1x]*
3. *How can governments better include the interests of different groups of citizens in their decisions during a epidemic? [0x]*
4. *How should governments communicate their crisis decisions to citizens? [3x]*
5. *Which other actors, apart from Bergen municipality and its citizens, should be involved? [1x]*
6. *Drawing on your experience of the Covid-19 crisis, which measures worked well, and which ones did not work well? [4x]*
7. *Do you think it is a good idea that Bergen municipality and the national government coordinate their decisions during an epidemic? If yes, why is this a good idea? [2x]*

3. Recommendations drafted

- *Which recommendations did citizens elaborate?*

A total of eleven recommendations were developed. Although the recommendation form included a field/cell for 'title', 'addressed to', 'description', and 'motivation' all groups used almost exclusively the field of 'description' which often also included the motivation. The recommendations of two sub-groups were addressed to the 'central government' and to 'national, regional, and local authorities'.

1. More accessible information channels, social media, text messages, local radio. A website that is updated continuously, functions as a secure source that makes it easy for individuals to access the latest information.

2. The government must create a good emergency plan if the other information channels are down. Information should be available at grocery stores. Air raid sirens.

3. The public sector must prioritize service telephones and create a contingency plan in the event of an emergency and people call much more than usual.

4. Crisis management should not be politically driven. The recommendation is to protect children and young people from isolating measures and conduct frequent assessments of the measures, and that it is communicated to the people via the right people (professionals must be up and coming). The purpose of frequent assessments is to ensure legitimacy throughout the crisis period.

5. Form an independent emergency council, with professional groups, interest organizations, voluntary emergency organizations (lawyers, health care, schools, industry, etc.) The purpose is to improve professional competence, communication, appropriate measures. Create a holistic picture of the situation.

6. Those who are going to communicate crisis decisions to the people must be experts and professionals in the field, who are also credible. Be honest with all information that is given.

7. Resources we need are money and professionals. We think that other actors are important are the government and professionals. We believe that professionals should form a professional panel that is formed by professionals with expertise in the different crises that occur and based on risk analysis. That is, to carry out a certain prevention.

8. Citizens' panel responds to things in BK (Bergen municipality transcript note?). Use them as help, if it is built up in such a way that it is a diversified group. Listen to them, feel that you are heard.

Disabled and pensioners as voluntary labor. Or people who have a lot of surplus. Motivate to participate in voluntary work and still do their job.

9. Minimum possible shutdown (a middle ground). Every other day at school, prioritize children and young people. Quick solutions such as teams in school. The cabin ban should have been handled differently. Sent home from FHS and the military. All occupational groups must be allowed to have protective equipment.

10. Primarily use all relevant digital and analogue means for raising initial awareness. This should as a minimum include the main issue and where further information is available. Initial measures (national) with expected reassessment dates, follow up local measures, make information available for minority languages.

11. Initially, any measure should be applicable on a national level. This should have a short timeframe before measures are reassessed. Once the situation is more transparent, measures can be changed, increased or decreased. Regional and local measures can be implemented in the following phases.

4. Debate and conflicting opinions

- *Which recommendations had conflicting opinions?*
- *On which recommendations was there agreement among the citizens?*

After the deliberation phase during which the four sub-groups drafted their recommendations, the citizens were asked to return to the common room for the plenary (between 14.45-15.15). Because of the break-down into four sub-groups, we were concerned with the number of recommendations that would be developed (up to sixteen) would preclude an extensive collective discussion with the whole group within 30 minutes. Hence, we decided to put the eleven recommendations in an excel file during a 20-minutes break which was projected on the screen during the plenary. The moderator (Sveinung Arnesen) explained that it was time-wise not possible to discuss each recommendation in detail, but citizens could vote on the importance of a recommendation that would enable the organizers to prioritize the recommendations. Each citizen received a green (very important), yellow (neutral), or red (not important) post-it, and they were asked to cast their vote after the moderator spoke out loud the recommendation and asked whether there were questions and unclarities about the recommendation. The outcome of the voting for each of the eleven recommendations is shown in the table below. It is important to note that during the voting process there were no questions or remarks, and the organizers noticed that some of the citizens seemed to look around at how other participants voted before deciding on their own vote.

Recommendation	Very important	Neutral	Not important	Abstain
1	17		1	
2	12	6		
3	9	8	1	
4	14	3	1	
5	15	1		2
6	14	3		1
7	7	10		1
8	10	4	1	3
9	11	6		1
10	11	3		4
11	14	4		

5. Suggestions for the future

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- *Which lessons to learn for the organization of future citizens' juries, which suggestions?*

We received 17 self-declaration forms from 18 participants. One participant (6%) indicated to not have received any formal education [*ingen formell utdanning*], five (29%), six (35%), and five (29%) participants indicated respectively secondary school [*vidergående skole*], a Bachelor degree [*Bachelorgrad*], or a Master degree [*Mastergrad*] as their highest level of completed education. An absolute majority of ten participants (59%) indicated to be full-time employees [*ansatt på heltid*], four citizens (24%) indicated to be retired [*pensjonist*], two citizens (12%) declared to be student [*student*], and one citizen (6%) indicated to be employed part-time [*ansatt på deltid*]. Citizen jury's are often criticized for not having a representative sample of the total population of citizens and to be biased towards highly-educated citizens (who tend to have a higher political interest and more political knowledge) and older and unemployed citizens (who tend to have more time to participate). About one-third of the participants (35%) in the Bergen citizen jury had secondary school or lower as their highest level of completed education, more than half of the participants (65%) indicated to have work, and a minority (24%) indicated to be retired. Hence, the degree of self-selection, and possible 'bias' resulting from this self-selection, should be relatively lower than usually is the case with a citizen jury. To increase participation of employed citizens and students and young people we decided to hold the citizen jury on a Saturday instead of a weekday. This may have helped with increasing the participation of these groups of citizens. In addition, citizens were invited through the municipality via a digital channel that is used for most post that is important and is sent by an official government or non-governmental organization.

6. Feedbacks from citizens

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- *What feedbacks did citizens report in their evaluation forms? (summary)*

All 18 participants completed the evaluation form. The participants were very positive. The participants gave an average grade of 4,5 to the citizen jury overall (1 = very badly; 5 = very well), the average importance grade for the topics discussed was 4,6 (1 = not important; 5 = very important), and the average grade for the organization of the event was 4,7 (1 = not good; 5 = very good).

All 18 participants (100%) felt free to express their opinion, 6 citizens (33%) thought that the citizen jury will have a concrete impact on future decisions whereas 12 citizens (67%) thought it will do so in part, and no less than 16 citizens (89%) is interested in taking part in similar events in the future whereas only 2 citizens (11%) were perhaps interested.

12 citizens (67%) indicated that the citizen jury met their expectations, for one citizen (6%) this was not the case, and for 5 citizens (28%) this was in part the case. 15 participants (83%) indicated that the duration of the citizen jury was adequate, for two participants (11%) it was too short, and one participant (6%) did not provide an answer.

All 18 participants (100%) wrote something down for at least one open answer survey question. 13 participants

(72%) indicated that they liked the group discussion the best, and 5 participants (28%) commended the structure of the citizen jury (expert input, two deliberation phases, plenary). The plenary could have been improved because 6 citizens (33%) preferred to have more discussion during the plenary and/or found the recommendations too long which made the voting procedure a bit complicated. 4 participants (22%) indicated that they would have preferred to discuss other crises as well, and to the question which topics they would prefer to discuss in future citizen jury's 8 participants (44%) mentioned nature (catastrophes), 4 participants (22%) wrote down climate or war, and two participants (11%) mentioned energy.

The citizens could leave other comments for the organizers and no less than 10 participants (56%) wrote down well done, good job, or thank you, and only two participants (11%) remarked that they wished that there would have been made more use of the Norwegian language.

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e. MWs Evaluation Form
Media workshop “Title”
Place, Date

How do you evaluate the workshop overall?

1 very badly	2	3	4	5 very well

Did the workshop meet your expectations?

- Yes
- No
- Only in part
- No answer

Which aspects did you like the most and which ones the least?

Do you think that the topics faced are important?

1 not important	2	3	4	5 very important

How do you evaluate the organization of the event?

1 Not good	2	3	4	5 Very good

Are you interested in taking part in similar events in the future?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- No answer

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What should be improved in the organization of such an event?

Other comments for the organizers:

Thank you for your participation!

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f. Output Document Form : Lessons Learned
MEDIA WORKSHOP (MW) OF XXX

1. Overview of the Media Workshop	
<i>Title / specific topic</i>	
<i>Date and location</i>	
<i>Local partner involved in the organization</i>	
<i>Pilot municipality/region in numbers (inhabitants, size)</i>	
<i>Number of participants</i>	
<i>How were participants invited?</i>	
<i>Speaker (name and profession)</i>	
<i>Facilitator (name and profession)</i>	
<i>How did the MW take place? Into how many phases was the MW structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).</i>	
<i>Which general considerations on the MW to report?</i>	
<i>Which challenges did the MW face?</i>	

<p><i>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the MW that should be pointed out?</i></p>	
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2. Key points from the discussions on the media's role in crisis management

- *What are the key points of the discussion?*
- *What takeaways did you gain from the workshop?*
- *Where there interesting points relevant to our final LEGITIMULT deliverables, such as policy recommendations?*

3. Feedbacks from participants

- *What feedbacks did participants report in their evaluation forms? (summary)*

g. Output Documents

MEDIA WORKSHOP (MW) OF UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERP

1. Overview of the Media Workshop	
<i>Title / specific topic</i>	Hoe berichtgeven over wetenschappelijk onderzoek? ["How should scientific research be communicated/reported?"]
<i>Date and location</i>	Antwerp, 15 May 2025; 14.00-16.30
<i>Local partner involved in the organization</i>	University of Antwerp Team composed of: Jakob Frateur and Peter Bursens
<i>Pilot municipality/region in numbers (inhabitants, size)</i>	Antwerp, ca. 500.000 inhabitants
<i>Number of participants</i>	21
<i>How were participants invited?</i>	This media workshop was part of a lecture for journalism students at the AP Hogeschool. Students needed to be present. Others were invited through targeted emails.
<i>Speaker (name and profession)</i>	Jakob Frateur, PhD researcher University of Antwerp
<i>Facilitator (name and profession)</i>	Peter Bursens, Professor University of Antwerp Wouter Frateur, Lecturer AP Hogeschool

<p><i>How did the MW take place? Into how many phases was the MW structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).</i></p>	Phase	Kort	Wie	Wat
	1	Introductie van het project (15min)	Universiteit Antwerpen (UA)	Voorstelling van de onderzoekers, het project en algemeen overzicht van de workshop.
	3	Inzichten uit het project (20min)	UA	Presentatie over de resultaten en inzichten van het LEGITIMULT project ivm. het politiek vertrouwen van burgers.
	4	Bespreking/brainstorm, eerst algemeen, daarna in kleinere groepen van 4-5 personen (45min)	Deelnemers, gemodereerd door UA en AP	Bespreking van de inzichten uit de resultaten van het onderzoek en mogelijkheid tot stellen van vragen aan betrokken onderzoekers. In deze fase proberen de studenten met enkele originele invalshoeken te komen om te berichten over de onderzoeksresultaten die ze net gezien hebben.
	5	Uitwerken invalshoek (45min)	Deelnemers	De deelnemers werken een van de invalshoeken die ze bedacht hebben verder uit en passen deze toe in een 'interview' met de betrokken onderzoekers.
	6	Conclusie (15min)	UA	Korte samenvatting workshop bedanking
<p><i>Which general considerations on the MW to report?</i></p>	<p>There were no professional journalists present, and the audience therefore consisted only of students. This impacted the discussions but also added an additional learning component for them – namely on how to report on scientific studies.</p>			
<p><i>Which challenges did the MW face?</i></p>	<p>Finding journalists that wanted to attend to workshop. This was partially anticipated or compensated by doing the workshop with students of journalism.</p>			
<p><i>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the MW that should be pointed out?</i></p>	<p>The organization went well due to good contacts between the University of Antwerp and the AP Hogeschool.</p>			

2. Key points from the discussions on the media's role in crisis management

We focused in our discussion on the way journalists can deal with scientific research and how to report on such research. We discussed, among others, the differences between interviewing politicians and scientists – with scientists often refraining from giving opinions and sticking to what they know and therefore requiring other types of questions that politicians. The points mentioned in the discussion were also put in practice during a mock interview of two experts on the topic (i.e., Peter Bursens and Jakob Frateur).

We further discussed possible angles to report in the media on scientific research results, in case results of the LEGITIMULT project, which were then further developed in the mentioned mock interviews. The participants got feedback on these interviews, both on the form and content of the questions. Finally, we shortly discussed the results of the research on political trust during the pandemic and the role the media could play in reporting or not certain aspects of crisis governance that could influence citizens' trust. This was, however, not the main goal of the workshop as there were no practitioners but served more as a reflection. There was some agreement that media should always be able to play their critical role, but also that they should not undermine crisis governance efforts.

3. Feedbacks from participants

Participants were skeptical at first, but most participants were enthusiast by the end of the workshop. Not only about the content, but also about the working methods. Some thought it was too long, but many indicated that they had learned something.

MEDIA WORKSHOP (MW) OF LJUBLJANA

1. Overview of the Media Workshop	
<i>Title / specific topic</i>	Crisis communication and media during the COVID-19 Pandemic and proposals for future crisis situations
<i>Date and location</i>	Ljubljana, 9 April 2025, 13:00-15:00
<i>Local partner involved in the organization¹</i>	Institute for Ethnic Studies (IES) Team composed of the IES researchers: Dr. Romana Bešter, Dr. Danijel Grafenauer, Dr. Janez Pirc, Dr. Sofija Zver, Prof. Dr. Mitja Žagar
<i>MW for the whole country</i>	Held at IES, Ljubljana, Slovenia
<i>Number of participants</i>	10
<i>How were participants invited?</i>	By phone, by e-mail
<i>Speakers and discussants</i>	<p>Introduction: Mitja Žagar</p> <p>Speakers and discussants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr. Sandra Bašić Hrvatin (professor at University of Primorska, Faculty of Humanities), • Dr. Janez Markeš (journalist of daily Delo), • Prof. Dr. Marko Milosavljevič (professor at University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Social Sciences), • Špela Novak (journalist at Radio Slovenia, Program 1). <p>Two participants, who were unable to attend and apologized for the MW (Janko Petrovc, journalist and editor in chief of Radio Koper/Capodistria; Tatjana Pirc – journalist at Radio Slovenia, Program 2 – Wave 202) were informed about the contents, recommendations and conclusions of the MW by phone. They agreed with them and their comments are included in this report.</p>
<i>Facilitator</i>	Mitja Žagar

¹ All persons in the form listed alphabetically by family name – with their academic titles when first mentioned.

<p><i>How did the MW take place? Into how many phases was the MW structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).</i></p>	<p>Workshop was organized as an open discussion of all participants, based upon the following agenda:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction: presentation of LEGITIMULT and MW. • Introductory remarks by participants on crisis communication and management, media, and their specific experiences and perceptions during the Covid-19 Pandemic. • Open discussion on: media legislation and system, infrastructure, organization and their functioning shortcomings particularly in crisis situations; crisis communication – particularly crisis communication protocols and crisis information; problems and shortcomings of infrastructure and technology for communication and information that are inadequate and not designed for crisis situations; the role of civil society and local communities. • Key lessons and recommendations • Conclusion
<p><i>Which general considerations on the MW to report?</i></p>	<p>Discussing the situation and experiences, it was stressed that the pandemic revealed shortcomings and problems in crisis management, communication and information as well as in the role and functioning of the media. However, it also demonstrated the benefits of internal cohesion of local communities, solidarity and interconnectedness, and different forms of civil society organisation in crisis response and better crisis resilience. For example, during the floods in Slovenia, local people with knowledge of the terrain, ability to reach locations that were cut off (because of destroyed roads, bridges and railroads), and personal connections and communication channels effectively compensated for the lack of rapid reactions by state and other authorities.</p> <p>This clearly demonstrated the importance of linking civil society and the state apparatus and showed that local knowledge and networks, which are not always integrated into larger systems, can play a key role in crisis management. In Slovenia, the civil and national protection services, and in particular the professional and volunteer firefighters, their associations brigades, have an excellent track record and are highly respected and trusted, having proved their worth in various crisis situations and natural disasters (e.g. floods, fires - including large wildfires, wind and ice storms, etc.).</p> <p>Discussing the process and role of crisis information, communication and the media in future crisis situations, the following challenges were detected and elaborated:</p>

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- Challenges in the legislation, media system, organization, funding and ownership, as well as situation, independence, professionalism, ethics, security and protection of journalists (including their jobs).
- During the pandemic, a number of measures related to the public media were called into question in Slovenia. In particular, it was a challenge to ensure the funding of public media and to adopt legislation that would allow the stable and normal functioning of RTVSLO (Radio Television Slovenia as the central public information service) and STA (Slovenian Press Agency as the public service used by all media), which play a key role in crisis information and communication. It is important that people trust and believe them. Announcements of legislative reforms to ensure the stable functioning and funding of public information services and to regulate the role and importance of the media in crisis communication have not materialised. This has proved problematic especially in crisis situations.
- There were also many problems in ensuring access to and dissemination of the media during the pandemic. Measures such as bans on the distribution of newspapers and magazines in public places led to a sharp drop in circulation, which further threatened the financial stability of the media, especially print media. The situation is slowly returning to normal since the end of the crisis, but - especially as regards print media circulation, funding (e.g. through advertising) and the distribution of other traditional media - has not returned to the pre-crisis period and level.

One of the key challenges Slovenia faced during the Covid-19 pandemic was the lack of preparedness and capacity for crisis communication. Crisis communication should be credible, well-founded, calm, polite, inclusive and understandable to all addressees and, above all, shall always respect and implement the highest professional and ethical standards. In Slovenia, during the pandemic, it was often judged inadequate and ineffective, in particular due to the lack of coordination of information and the lack of trust in government representatives. Courts, which have judged the legality of individual crisis measures taken by the executive, have played a key role in restraining and/or reversing illegal (restrictive and repressive) measures. However, these illegal measures and policies have been in place for at least some time and have had negative consequences for people, and systemic mechanisms to prevent the misuse of crisis management, approaches and measures should be ensured in advance.

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	A significant factor in the less successful and legitimate crisis management and crisis communication and information was the lack of infrastructural support. In the case of a pandemic, as well as other crisis situations (floods), there were shortcomings in the communication systems, which prevented an effective response. The example of Norway, where the analogue infrastructure for emergencies was restored after an initial phase of digitisation, is a good illustration of the importance of having a diverse communications infrastructure that does not only rely on mobile phones or the internet, but also includes satellite phones, land lines and other forms of back-up systems.
<i>Which challenges did the MW face?</i>	X
<i>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the MW that should be pointed out?</i>	X

2. Key points from the discussions on the media's role in crisis management

- *What are the key points of the discussion?*
- *What takeaways did you gain from the workshop?*
- *Where there interesting points relevant to our final LEGITIMULT deliverables, such as policy recommendations?*

Key lessons and recommendations

Based on the experience of crisis management, information and communication during the COVID-19 pandemic, some key lessons and recommendations for the future can be highlighted:

- Legislative reform: There is an urgent need for legislative reform to allow for more stable functioning of the media, in particular the public information services, and adequate funding for RTVSLO and STA.
- Increase pro-activity in crisis communication: Crisis communication must be pre-planned, adequately technically equipped and trained, and credible in order to maintain public trust.
- Strengthening the crisis infrastructure: It is important to ensure a variety of communication channels that do not only rely on digital platforms but also include analogue systems such as radio frequencies and local communication channels.
- The role of civil society: It is important that in the future more emphasis is placed on the importance of strengthening local communities and civic networks that can react quickly and effectively in crisis situations.

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Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted several shortcomings in the crisis management and communication system, but these problems are also opportunities for improvement. The key is to prepare for future crisis situations with appropriate legislative, infrastructural and communication mechanisms to enable rapid and effective action and crisis.

3. Feedbacks from participants

- *What feedbacks did participants report in their evaluation forms? (summary)*

Based upon the conversations with the participants and their evaluations, we could conclude that all participants were very satisfied with the MW and pointed that such activities are very much needed and should be more frequent. They commended the contents, recommendations and conclusions, considering them very useful. However, they expressed that, unfortunately, the key decision-makers often do not pay attention to such events, their conclusions and recommendations.

Their evaluation was that the debate was wide, frank, fact based and solution oriented.

MEDIA WORKSHOP (MW) OF STOCKHOLM

1. Overview of the Media Workshop	
<i>Title / specific topic</i>	“Lessons from Covid-19 Journalism in a Post-Pandemic Future”
<i>Date and location</i>	Stockholm, 10 April 2025, 9:30-13:00 am
<i>Local partner involved in the organization</i>	International IDEA
<i>Pilot municipality/region in numbers (inhabitants, size)</i>	Stockholm, Sweden (1,738,000)
<i>Number of participants</i>	Total of those who attended: 15 We received confirmations from 14 individuals: 7 who later cancelled and 7 who ultimately did not attend the event without notifying us.
<i>How were participants invited?</i>	Via email, social media, professional contacts
<i>Speaker (name and profession)</i>	Mr. Alistair Scrutton, Head of Communications and Knowledge Management team at International IDEA Ms. Gentiana Gola, Democracy Assessment Adviser at International IDEA and Legitimult Project Coordinator Dr. Alexander Hudson, Democracy Assessment Senior Adviser at International IDEA and Legitimult Researcher Dr. Peter Bursens, Professor at the Department of Political Science at University of Antwerp, and Legitimult Co-Leader/ Researcher on Crisis, Governance and Trust
<i>Facilitator (name and profession)</i>	Navidip Dhariwal, Communications expert, former BBC correspondent

<p><i>How did the MW take place? Into how many phases was the MW structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).</i></p>	<p>09:30 – 10:00 Registration Welcome coffee and light breakfast</p> <p>10:00 – 10:10 Opening remarks and overview of the workshop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alistair Scrutton, Head of Communications and Knowledge Management team at International IDEA • Gentiana Gola, Democracy Assessment Adviser at International IDEA and Legitimult Project Coordinator • Dr Alexander Hudson, Democracy Assessment Senior Adviser at International IDEA and Legitimult Researcher <p>10:10 – 10:20 Introductions and overview of discussions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introductions of the group and expectations for the workshop • Overview of the session structure, objectives, and desired outcomes <p>Facilitated by Navdip Dhariwal, Communications expert, former BBC correspondent</p> <p>10:20 – 10:50 Presentation of relevant findings by Legitimult & Q&A</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Peter Bursens, Professor at the Department of Political Science at University of Antwerp, and Legitimult co-Leader/Researcher on Crisis, Governance and Trust <p>10:50 – 11:30 Part I – Group discussion: Public trust during crisis and the role of media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The relationship between government transparency and media accountability • The rise of misinformation and disinformation and how to combat it • Journalism in crisis governance and intergovernmental decision-making <p>11:30 – 11:40 Coffee break</p> <p>11:40 – 12:30 Part II – Group discussion: Public trust during crisis and the role of media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploring how to balance urgency and accuracy in breaking news • Ethical and transparent crisis reporting <p>12:30 – 13:00 Concluding remarks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations for strengthening media resilience in future crises • Closing remarks <p>13:00 – 14:00 Lunch at International IDEA Informal networking and opportunity for follow-up discussions</p>
<p><i>Which general considerations on the MW to report?</i></p>	<p>The event was a great success, featuring engaging and interactive discussions. These were particularly enriched by the participation of journalists who had covered Covid-19, alongside young and ambitious journalism students. The journalists’ insights helped bridge theory with real-world challenges, adding depth to the conversation. The facilitator’s own background in journalism also contributed meaningfully to the flow and quality of discussions.</p> <p>A valuable highlight was the presence of Dr. Peter Bursens from the University of Antwerp, who presented key findings from the LEGITIMULT project on trust. Additionally, the promotional materials provided to participants were well received, and the light breakfast, coffee break, and concluding lunch created a welcoming atmosphere that encouraged networking and extended conversations, which continued even after the event officially ended.</p>
<p><i>Which challenges did the MW face?</i></p>	<p>Despite leveraging International IDEA’s contacts database, engaging a consultant with access to journalists based in Sweden, reaching out through colleagues’ networks in journalism and communications, creating an event page on IDEA’s website, and heavily</p>

	<p>promoting the event on social media, securing confirmed in-person attendance proved somewhat challenging. That said, we did manage to receive over 20 confirmations.</p> <p>Unfortunately, several participants cancelled at the last minute—some on the morning of the event—leaving us unable to adjust the catering accordingly. Additionally, around half of those who had confirmed did not attend and did not notify us.</p> <p>Anticipating a larger group, we had booked the main conference room, which appeared somewhat empty with fewer attendees. Moreover, the majority of participants ended up being students rather than professional journalists, which may have affected the dynamic and posed a challenge for the journalists who were present. This mismatch in audience composition was likely the main challenge we faced. Nonetheless, the quality of the discussions was excellent. The smaller group size seemed to create a safer, more comfortable environment, allowing all participants to engage actively and have space to share their thoughts.</p>
<p><i>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the MW that should be pointed out?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deciding the topic and subtopics; • Aligning those with LEGITIMULT findings; • Finding a qualified facilitator who has experience, and is able to tie the topic and the understanding of journalists with the LEGITIMULT findings, while ensuring an interactive discussion; • Ensuring participation, especially of journalists: they tend to be busy, have last minute tasks. The fact that we didn't provide a fee or pay for the trip to Stockholm, made it less appealing for many of them to join; • Logistics: Booking catering, promotion (event page creation in the website, designing materials: agenda, event poster, registration templates, slides etc., social media promotion, online registration page, other templates like evaluation, registration, consent forms etc.), tracking dietary restrictions for catering and updating accordingly, last minute cancellations/ensuring participation, accommodation/travel booking, meetings with the facilitator to prepare the agenda/discussions etc. • Post-event work: payments, post-event article and blog, social media promotion, filling and scanning forms, email to participants with report from the event, pictures, slides etc.

2. Key points from the discussions on the media's role in crisis management

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What are the key points of the discussion?</i> - The need for consistent and coherent messaging, particularly in the early stages of a crisis. - The danger of fragmented or contradictory narratives. - Recognition that journalists may not always be equipped to cover crises in depth, leading to strong calls for specialist journalism - Urgency cannot come at the cost of accuracy, nuance and public understanding - During complex crises, journalistic objectivity should not necessarily equate to constant skepticism, but rather to fair engagement with authoritative expertise - The need to strengthen digital literacy across all generations to acknowledge the reality of echo chambers and the influence of unverified social media figures - AI technologies can be both a challenge and an opportunity; they can amplify misinformation but also support verification, fact-checking and enhanced media engagement if deployed responsibly <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What takeaways did you gain from the workshop?</i> • <i>Where there interesting points relevant to our final LEGITIMULT deliverables, such as policy recommendations?</i> <p>For Governments and Public Institutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fund independent, public interest journalism. - Coordinate communication across government levels to maintain coherent messaging. - Invest in media literacy education to empower citizens to evaluate information sources critically. <p>For Journalists and Media Organisations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and support specialist reporting roles. - Avoid performative skepticism toward credible experts. - Clarify uncertainties in real-time. <p>For Civil Society and Academia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourage cross-sector partnerships. - Promote peer-to-peer training models. - Explore the role of AI tools in supporting verification and fact-based reporting.

3. Feedbacks from participants

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What feedback did participants report in their evaluation forms? (summary)</i> <p>Total evaluations received: 8 Participants who gave full marks (5 being best): 5 Participants who gave less than full marks: 3 (marks: 3,3,4)</p>

Overall feedback: The filled in evaluation forms from the participants indicated that the workshop was perceived as welcoming and open, with an atmosphere that allowed everyone to express their thoughts. The facilitator received positive remarks, and the discussions were described as engaging and reflective of different perspectives. It was mentioned that the workshop was well organized, comprehensive and inclusive.

Areas for improvement: Several comments expressed a wish for a more diverse group of participants including more media representatives, working professionals and experts. One also wished for more information on the fellow participants and discussion topics beforehand. Additionally, it was noted that the discussion tended to be too EU-centric.

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MEDIA WORKSHOP (MW) OF BOLZANO/BOZEN

1. Overview of the Media Workshop	
<i>Title / specific topic</i>	Comunicare le crisi: Il ruolo dei media / Krisen kommunizieren: Die Rolle der Medien ["Communicating crisis: The role of the media"]
<i>Date and location</i>	Bolzano/Bozen, 15 May 2025, 8:30-11:00 am
<i>Local partner involved in the organization</i>	Eurac Research Institute for Comparative Federalism Team composed of: Greta Klotz, Günther Pallaver, Petra Malfertheiner, Francisco Javier Romero Caro, Chiara Salati.
<i>Pilot municipality/region in numbers (inhabitants, size)</i>	106,357 inhabitants approximately. This represents 19.8% of the total population of South Tyrol (Source: https://www.autonomy-dashboard.info/it). 52.30 km ²
<i>Number of participants</i>	10
<i>How were participants invited?</i>	They were invited through targeted individual invitations and internal communication from the Trentino-Alto Adige/South Tyrol Journalists' Association.
<i>Speaker (name and profession)</i>	Prof. Günther Pallaver Senior Researcher at Eurac Research Institute for Comparative Federalism, Professor at the University of Innsbruck – Department of Political Science, and journalist.
<i>Facilitator (name and profession)</i>	Petra Malfertheiner, Researcher at Eurac Research Institute for Comparative Federalism. Francisco Javier Romero Caro, Senior Researcher at Eurac Research Institute for Comparative Federalism.
<i>How did the MW take place? Into how many phases was the MW structured? (you can paste here also the agenda of the event).</i>	<p>After an initial introduction by Greta Klotz on the LEGITIMULT project and its objectives, a presentation was held by the expert Prof. Günther Pallaver on the general topic of media and crises.</p> <p>The core of the workshop was the group activity where participants representing local media (print, radio, tv, online) and communication managers (institutional, NGO) were split into groups. They had the chance to discuss their experience with crisis management under the guidance of</p>

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	<p>some journalists/communication managers (Simonetta Nardin, Silvia Franceschini, Paolo Mazzucato, Margit Piok).</p> <p>In the plenary session, the two groups presented the outcomes and “lessons learnt” from the group work. Together with the facilitation by the researcher Petra Malfertheiner, also Francisco Javier Romero Caro, senior researcher closely involved in the LEGITIMULT project, provided feedback based on the project’s general findings. The general conclusions were drawn by prof. Günther Pallaver.</p> <p>Reflecting the bilingual context of the pilot area, the workshop was held in bilingual mode (Italian and German): each participant was free to use the language of their preference.</p> <p>Programme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8:30-9:00 Welcoming and introduction / Benvenuto e introduzione / Willkommen und Einleitung Greta Klotz (Eurac Research) • 9:00-9:30 Presentation “Communicating risks and crises” / Präsentation: “Risiko- und Krisenkommunikation / Presentazione: Comunicazione dei rischi e della crisi” Prof. Günther Pallaver (Eurac Research) • 9:30-10:10 Group work and presentation / Lavoro di Gruppo e presentazioni / Arbeit in Kleingruppen und Präsentation (Simonetta Nardin, Silvia Franceschini, Paolo Mazzucato, Margit Piok) • 10:10-10:45 Plenary session / Plenaria / Plenum Moderated by / Moderato da / moderiert von Petra Malfertheiner (Eurac Research) • 10:45-11:00 Concluding remarks / Conclusione / Abschluss Prof. Günther Pallaver (Eurac Research) <p>The input questions to facilitate the discussion were the following: The overall question: How to manage communication in emergency situations? (<i>pandemic, heatwaves, blackouts, landslides, chemical accidents, large-scale fires, floods, train accidents...</i>)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What mistakes should be avoided, looking back at how communication was handled during the pandemic? • How could the flow of information between institutions (especially at the provincial level, but also regional, national government, ministries, parliament, WHO) and the media be improved?
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How should uncertain and incomplete information be managed? • How can we communicate transparently that, in emergencies, knowledge is often partial? • How to address the challenge of parallel communication via social media (e.g. by bloggers, mayors, "influencers", etc.)? • How can a balance between expert opinions be achieved? • How to ensure balanced coverage in times of fake news and declining trust in the media? How can fact-checking and media literacy be strengthened? • Is access to institutional information (especially at the provincial level, but also regional, national, ministerial, and parliamentary) equal for all media outlets? • Were local and regional media adequately involved during the pandemic? How could they be better integrated into crisis communication in the future? • How can different population groups (age, languages, minorities) be reached? • How important is it to build and maintain collaborations (including international ones) between institutions and the media in "quiet" times? • How useful would a standardized crisis communication plan be?
<p><i>Which general considerations on the MW to report?</i></p>	<p>The MW was a successful event: the participants were very interested in the topic and underlined the importance of the exchange among peers about the extraordinary situation during the pandemic. They also admitted that so far (in their respective editorial offices/teams) there has not been any real evaluation of the experiences during the pandemic.</p> <p>As organizers we are particularly pleased with the idea born during the group work about creating a “Bolzano/Bozen Charter” on crisis communication for media professionals (including journalists, but also communication managers, bloggers, sociologists etc.). Ideally, such a Charter would constitute a starting point for journalists and communicators of the region Trentino-Alto Adige/South Tyrol to reflect together on crisis communication, starting from the Covid-19 pandemic case. The aim of such a Charter would be to initiate a more structured process of reflection to share ideas and personal considerations on what to learn from that pandemic period, what not to replicate in future crises, and what to improve in the communication of future crises. A special consideration was made regarding the “Code of Ethics of Journalists” that other communicators (bloggers, online commentators etc.) are not legally bound by. Once such a process is finalized, the Charter should clearly define up-to-date guidelines on how to communicate a crisis.</p>

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	While this was just a spur-of-the-moment idea, after having facilitated this first step, we hope these 10 participants will take the leadership to follow up on such an initiative.
<i>Which challenges did the MW face?</i>	The main challenge was the design of an interesting format that would not only attract participants, but that would have a concrete impact on the work of media professionals and communication officers.
<i>What were the main critical aspects in the organization of the MW that should be pointed out?</i>	The main critical aspect was the delayed invitation of participants, and the limited dissemination of this initiative beyond the network of the journalists' association. As organizers, we relied too much on their capacity to promote the event, but we later found out that their communication efforts were minimal. By the time we reached out directly to (around 20) media professionals and communication officers, their agenda was already filled. Several of them replied that such a workshop would have been of great interest to their organization had it been communicated earlier.

2. Key points from the discussions on the media's role in crisis management

- *What are the key points of the discussion?*
- *What takeaways did you gain from the workshop?*
- *Where there interesting points relevant to our final LEGITIMULT deliverables, such as policy recommendations?*

Key points of the discussion

- General role of journalists during a crisis
- Media professionals' mistakes during the Covid-19 crisis communication
- Difficulties faced by journalists during the Covid-19 crisis
- Lack of guidelines for media professionals on how to work properly during a crisis
- Lessons learned during the pandemic

Recommendations emerged

1. Journalists should avoid chasing "the void" and uncertainty in the immediate outbreak of a crisis. They should not pursue uncertainty, but rather offer a framework for reasoning, instead of simply responding to the pressure to "make news".
2. Journalists should have the courage and sincerity to admit that, at present, there are no certainties about a particular crisis situation, and instead say, "We ourselves do not fully

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understand what is happening.” It is more useful to clearly state the facts that are known for sure.

3. Journalists should make a commitment not to turn a crisis or emergency into an opportunity for audience ratings or clickbaiting. Gaining an audience is not the same as providing information.
4. Journalists should continue to do fact-checking and accept the structural weakness of being delayed in reporting a crisis: at least this ensures the coverage is accurate.
5. It is important to build a “media competence” or “science competence” for citizens, not only for youth in schools but also for older generations.
6. It would be useful to update the (crossborder) ethical codes of journalism associations by including specific sections on how to act and proceed in certain crisis management situations.
7. Local media should be strengthened (in terms of finance and staff).
8. It is important to establish networks outside of crisis situations in “peaceful” times.
9. Social media channels should be moderated better.

Key takeaways from the discussion

- Media are guarantors of democracy to “educate” the citizens also during a crisis: they have the very delicate role of providing information to citizens so that they can create their own opinion on certain matters.
- It would be needed to have a serious discussion and shared reflection on the mistakes made by media professionals during the pandemic: it should be a serious and bipartisan process, going beyond party divisions, so that it can truly be neutral and trustworthy.
- The participants acknowledged that there has never been a moment when media professionals made the point to say that the pandemic-crisis period has finished and that as a category they should start a phase of common reflection before proceeding. Actually, a clear defining moment marking a pre and post would be necessary in times of crisis. The elaboration of the pandemic is a complex process and more difficult than the elaboration of other (smaller) crisis moments.
- On provincial level, a process of crisis communication together with the civil protection was started and should produce some guiding lines and information for media with regard to responsible persons / contacts etc during crises.
- While journalists follow a code of ethics, other communicators (bloggers, opinionists on social media) are not bound by such standards. This absence of ethical standards for non-journalistic communicators can blur the line between fact and opinion, fuel misinformation and sensationalism, and ultimately erode public trust in credible journalism.
- It would be needed to create a code of ethics on the use of AI.

3. Feedbacks from participants

- *What feedbacks did participants report in their evaluation forms? (summary)*

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General feedback:

The main feedback was that participants thanked the organizers for creating this opportunity for open dialogue and starting the debate on crisis communication taking the Covid-19 pandemic as the main example. For the first time since the pandemic, they found themselves reflecting on how communication is managed during a crisis, in this way questioning their roles, acknowledging past mistakes, and considering what should be done differently moving forward.

More specific feedback as emerged from the participants' evaluation forms:

The overall feedback of the event was very positive: All participants rated the event with 4 or 5 out of 5 points, indicating a high level of overall satisfaction. The topic was also considered highly relevant by everyone, with only the top two rating categories (4 and 5) being selected. The overall organization of the event was rated very positively as well.

Furthermore, all participants agreed that they would attend again if similar events were organized in the future. Regarding whether their expectations were met, 7 out of 10 participants said yes, while 3 stated that their expectations were only partially met.

In the open comments, some participants provided concrete feedback and particularly appreciated the open discussion and the exchange within the small groups. Critical remarks included that the available time was too short, and the initial phase felt somewhat disoriented.

Additionally, three participants mentioned that the invitation was sent too late and that the event was not advertised enough. One participant also noted that there may have been too many questions asked.

